

D1.1 Methodology for Assessing the Ethics, Transparency, Accountability, and Privacy of AI-Based Systems in CCAM APPLICATIONS

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The AITHENA D1.1 document provides a comprehensive methodology for evaluating the ethical, transparent, accountable, and privacy-preserving aspects of Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications in Cooperative, Connected, and Automated Mobility (CCAM). This document, a product of collaborative efforts by various experts from multiple institutions, is underpinned by the goal of enhancing the trustworthiness of AI technologies in mobility systems.

The project articulates an intricate structure for the evaluation process across four main pillars—fairness, transparency, accountability, and privacy. These categories are essential for building AI systems that are not only technically proficient but also ethically aligned and socially acceptable. The document introduces a set of checklists and guidelines tailored for developers and testers of CCAM functions, ensuring that the technologies developed are centred around human needs and adhere to rigorous ethical standards.

The key themes and objectives revolve around human-centric AI, ethical frameworks and assessment and operationalisation of trustworthiness. AITHENA places a strong emphasis on human-centric approaches, stressing the importance of aligning AI applications with the needs and rights of all stakeholders, including vulnerable populations. This approach is evident in the project's dedication to integrating ethical considerations into the development lifecycle of AI technologies.

This document reviews existing ethical frameworks and adapts them to the unique challenges posed by CCAM applications. It also proposes new frameworks where necessary to cover gaps in current methodologies. Through its checklists, AITHENA operationalizes concepts such as fairness, accountability, privacy, and transparency, making them tangible and actionable for developers and regulators alike. This includes detailed guidelines for assessing the social impact of AI technologies and ensuring they contribute positively to societal well-being.

The methodologies developed in the AITHENA project (through innovation in technical WPs) are expected to influence not only future AI developments in the mobility sector but also broader discussions on AI ethics in other domains. By setting high standards for fairness, transparency, accountability and privacy, the project contributes to the global discourse on responsible AI, promoting practices that can lead to more robust and reliable AI systems.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	MEANING
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AV	Autonomous Vehicles
A/IS	Autonomous and Intelligent Systems
ADC	Agent-Deed Consequence
CAD	Connected and Automated Driving
CAV	Connected and Automated Vehicles
CCAM	Connected and Cooperative Automated Mobility
DMA	Digital Markets Act
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
DSA	Digital Services Act
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standard Institute
EVT	Ethical Valence Theory
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HIC	Human in Command
HITL	Human in the Loop
HLEG	High-Level Expert Group
HOTL	Human on the Loop
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
MES	Mandatory Ethics Setting
ML	Machine Learning
NGO	Non-governmental Organization
NHTSA	National Highway Traffic Safety Administration
ODD	Operational Design Domain
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PbD	Privacy by Design
PES	Personal Ethical Setting
RACI	Responsible, Accountable, Consulted, Informed
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SOTIF	Safety of the Intended Functionality
SRA	Socially Responsible AI Algorithms
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
VSD	Value Sensitive Design
WP	Work Package
XAI	Explainable AI

PREFACE

AITHENA, among many other projects and initiatives, is advancing the possibilities for driverless vehicle technologies using artificial intelligence. These technological advances have the potential to improve the lives of people in both urban and rural areas by eliminating speeding and dangerous driving, by preventing vehicle crashes caused by human error, by addressing the driver shortage in public transport and by parking themselves away from neighbourhood streets where children play and where more green space is needed. Despite these positive effects, driverless vehicles have their critics. Some are concerned about the “black box” effect that does not allow the user of a driverless car – or those who are outside it – to understand what decisions it makes, and on what basis. Others are concerned about a “Big Brother State”, not wanting their movements to be tracked by vehicles or infrastructure as they travel through public space. Users of self-driving cars may have concerns about being held responsible if a crash happened in a self-driving car in which they were an occupant. And finally, many people have heard stories of artificial intelligence systems not recognising people with a non-white skin colour, female voices or those sitting in a wheelchair.

It is important that all citizens can feel safe and at ease in their city and that travellers can be (and feel) safe and comfortable on streets and roads in both urban and rural settings. This includes physical **safety** – regardless of their size, shape, gender, skin colour, physical (dis)ability or other factors. It also includes peace of mind that they (and any children or others for whom they care) can travel safely around their city on foot or by bicycle, knowing that their personal data is not being captured or stored without their consent.

This document consists of an introductory background chapter, which establishes a broad ethical context for human-centred AI-based **CCAM** functions. It then provides guidance along four different aspects of human-centricity. These are: fairness, transparency, accountability and **privacy**.

Target audience

- The primary audience for this set of checklists and guidance is **developers and testers of CCAM functions or systems**. For this audience, the checklists offer a broad perspective on the many aspects of trustworthiness that should be taken into account to ensure that any planned CCAM function is human-centric.
- A second audience for AITHENA’s checklists and guidance is **local authorities** (for port areas, industrial parks, airports, etc.) who are considering inviting/allowing the use of driverless vehicles in their jurisdictions. For this audience, the checklists may suggest content for possible calls for tender or provide questions to ask of CCAM providers to ensure the systems being offered meet the needs of the city and its citizens.
- The third audience for these checklist and guidance is **regulators**, for whom it could be valuable as they try to determine what should be allowed, under what conditions and what possible regulatory pitfalls they should look out for.
- A fourth possible audience could be **citizens**, so that they can understand both the complexity of the topic and their own rights, whether they be users of driverless vehicles or those who may find themselves outside of such vehicles.

Structure

The deliverable begins with the status quo on ethics in AI-enabled CCAM applications focusing on its lawfulness, ethical frameworks and principles, and **robustness**. This is followed by four checklists, one each for each of the trustworthiness-related topics identified as critical to ensure human-centred AI-based CCAM functions. These are: fairness, transparency, accountability and privacy. It must be acknowledged that there are many overlaps among the different aspects of trustworthiness discussed in this deliverable. The document begins with an overview of ethics in general, making it clear that this ethical choices and actions go far beyond the “trolley question”, posing the hypothetical question of whose life should be sacrificed and whose should be saved (in effect: Whose life is more valuable?) in the situation of an unavoidable crash where one will survive. While the awareness that such ethical questions cannot be made by programmers it is critical to be aware of where and how such decisions are being made, this is only one aspect of many. The AITHENA project reached the conclusion that a small set of indicators would not be enough to establish whether a given CCAM function or system addresses the many and complex components that make it human-centred. Instead, a set of checklists was developed. These are intended for use by developers and testers of AI-based CCAM functions. They can be used to reflect on an existing system or function or can be used in the development of a new one.

Each chapter begins with a short introduction to the concerns it addresses. This is followed by a checklist for developers or testers to refer to in the development of AI-based CCAM functions. Each checklist question refers to a specific section in the chapter in question, where further information and/or links to tools are provided for the human-centric development of AI-based CCAM. This format makes it easier for users to see what points may be of concern to them – or what issues they may not yet have considered – and takes them directly to a relevant source of information. In this way, it’s possible to move about the document, taking prompts from the questions and finding out more about the topic in question.

How to use this tool

The chapters evaluating fairness, transparency, accountability and privacy in AI-based CCAM application include a set of checklist questions (intended to prompt reflection amongst the target audience of AI-based CCAM functions) at the beginning. Majority of the questions are in a binary format, i.e. either yes or a no, where each question links directly to a paragraph in the chapter providing examples and/or references for further reading on the topic to help the reader consider the relevant aspects of fairness, transparency, accountability and privacy. While a quantitative response is not possible in every case, the questions help the readers navigate through different aspects of the human-centricity and allows them to either return to the checklist or continue reading through the document. There is no “pass or fail” grade as this would be difficult to quantify and is different from situation to situation.

Human-centricity means much more than making people feel safe while travelling in a driverless vehicle. If driverless vehicles are to be adopted at a larger scale, they need to be able to consider both those inside and outside the vehicle. Each chapter of the document also contains a section identifying challenges or gaps in research or knowledge. The topic of AI and CCAM are both in fairly early stages, and the combination of these is even newer, with many open questions. This document is a snapshot in time (mid-2023 to mid-24) of what issues are faced. It should be built upon and further developed where an approach using checklists is a more appropriate one than a set of indicators focussing not only on algorithms and sensors, but also beyond. A clear and shared understanding of terminology is very important in this context. For this reason, the glossary of terms is developed, which the readers will find towards the end of this deliverable.

1. INTRODUCTION: BACKGROUND and CONTEXT

1.1 Basic Assumptions for Ethics in AI-enabled CCAM Applications

1.1.1 Human-centric AI

AITHENA is a research and innovation project on Connected and Cooperative Automated Mobility (CCAM) solutions that aims to build *trustworthy, explainable, and accountable* CCAM technologies. The three adjectives associated with CCAM technologies in this description mean little without humans as the reference point. **The human-centric perspective is therefore the first of two working assumptions for this project.** It is also a core element of the European Union's strategy on AI, which frames the technology not as an end but a means to serve people with the aim of increasing human well-being (EC 2019). An alternative version of this argument calls on human-centric AI to amplify rather than erode human agency (Shneiderman 2021). Placing people at the centre of ethical AI-enabled CCAM applications has an empirical basis as well. A recent survey of AI developers and users found discrepancies between the two groups in ascribing values to certain principles. For instance, users considered the social impact of AI a much higher priority than developers did. Achieving human-centric AI is difficult if the interests and needs of different stakeholders diverge significantly (Bingley et al., 2023). This approach also calls for looking into the aspects of biasness and value-neutrality.

1.1.2 Holistic Approach

The second working assumption in AITHENA is to **take a holistic approach when analysing ethics in AI-enabled CCAM applications.** This position is a consequence of the first assumption (that human-centric AI is not value neutral) in combination with an emphasis on the "Cs" in CCAM. CCAM applications are both *connected* and *cooperative* amongst each and embedded in a larger infrastructure consisting (in part) of drivers/occupants and passengers of autonomous and non-autonomous vehicles as well as other forms of transportation, such as walking, cycling or public transport. Widening the circle of stakeholders in this way embeds citizens in broader societal and technological ecosystems alongside various public and private entities. Their inclusion as active participants can strengthen public trust in AI systems, improve collective decision making for AI-related policies, and empower regulatory bodies to support the development of AI for the common good (Sigfrids et al., 2023).

The assumption of a holistic approach is closely related to three objectives generally applicable to digital ethics:

- (1) The **theoretical aim**: to provide and justify arguments, criteria, or principles that provide guidelines for practical evaluations. These guidelines already include several considerations with universal claims of validity, such as fairness, societal wellbeing, and human rights.
- (2) The **practical aim**: a proactive evaluation of technological applications in their respective contexts.
- (3) The **diagnostic analysis** for each component of the application: a highly context-specific investigation into the impact of a technology that the previous two elements converge in.

A holistic approach to ethics in AI-enabled CCAM requires asking what difference the development and implementation of this technology makes compared to other means (Pfeiffer et al. 2023).

Figure 1: A systemic approach to human-centred AI development and deployment (Source: Sigfrids et al. 2023)

The pathway should also think beyond algorithmic fairness and connect major aspects of AI that potentially cause AI's indifferent behaviour. This relates to developing socially responsible AI algorithms (SRAs) (Cheng et al., 2021), which prioritizes the need of all stakeholders as the topmost priority, especially the minority and disadvantaged groups, to make just and trustworthy decisions.

Figure 2: An overview of socially responsible algorithms research (Source: Cheng et al. 2021)

Ethics in AI is an emerging field with several (disciplinary) blind spots and research gaps. This implies that the methodology for evaluating ethics in AI-based CCAM applications presented here is only a snapshot in time. Given a technology very much in flux and in limited use, there cannot be a claim to comprehensiveness, but rather a recognition of both a paradox and an opportunity. The paradox concerns the idea of participation in a flourishing debate on the ethics of AVs without being able to embed this conversation in ethics of transportation, which is not (yet) a well-established discipline (Santoni de Sio, 2021). The lack of such a framework is also an opportunity: combined with the need for a human-centric and holistic approach, to start a systematic discussion of essential features for an AI system, beginning with its trustworthiness.

1.2 Trustworthy AI-enabled CCAM Applications: Lawful, ethical, and robust

Mobility and transport as an “essential enabler of our economic and social life” matter to all of us – as do their negative externalities in the form of accidents and pollution (Fernandez & Gomez 2021). Autonomous vehicles promise to alleviate some of these costs, but their large-scale deployment, as rationalised by safety and sustainability arguments and underpinned by EU legislation and other regulatory regimes, requires trust as a “fundamental factor for seamless human-automation interaction”. This condition raises definitional questions because trust to a person and trust to an AI-based autonomous driving system looks different. For a person, trust can be expressed as a function of “competency” and “character”, while the functional equivalents for an autonomous driving system include “certification” and “intent and integrity” (Kanak et al., 2022). Other researchers reject trust as a concept applicable to AI because it humanises a technology and reduces the scope of human responsibility involved in its development and deployment. Their preferred term is “reliance” based on an understanding of trust as an inherently emotive state reserved for human beings. But even they concede that AI meets the requirements of a rational account of trust, which is a decision-making process based on predictive (rather than motivational) choices and thus within the realm of expectations for an algorithmically driven technology (Ryan, 2020).

Figure 3. The three components of trustworthy AI and embedded principles (adapted from AI HLEG 2019)

Since this document is concerned with constructing a systemic evaluation methodology, there is a need to prioritise the practical over the philosophical by providing parameters that guides our understanding of trustworthiness. The approach taken by the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) derives notions of trustworthiness primarily from the legal context (IEEE 2022) of the United States, whose current regulatory landscape tends to be more permissive than that of the EU. Therefore, this deliverable prefers the definition of trustworthiness by the European Commission’s AI High Level Expert Group with the following requirements:

Trustworthy AI should be:

- 1) **lawful** (i.e., compliant with all applicable laws and regulations),
- 2) **ethical** (adhering to **ethical principles** and values) and
- 3) **robust** (from a technical and social perspective to prevent unintentional harm).

1.2.1 Lawfulness

Lawful AI-based CCAM refers to the use of AI technologies in CCAM systems while adhering to legal and ethical principles¹. It ensures that AI algorithms and systems comply with applicable laws, regulations, and standards, as well as ethical considerations. Some examples of relevant laws that require compliance relate to road safety, data protection, cybersecurity, and privacy, but social welfare laws, such as human rights, also play a role. Legal frameworks differ across jurisdictions, so it is essential to also adhere to local laws governing the deployment, testing, and operation of autonomous vehicles and AI systems. Furthermore, the legal aspect of liability and accountability in relation to an illegal action performed by a CCAM vehicle at any point needs to be considered (discussed in Chapter 4). When approaching the lawfulness of AI-based CCAM from a human-centred perspective, the integration of AI technologies in CCAM systems is explored with respect to their development and deployment in a manner that respects human-centric values, such as ensuring safety and fostering public trust, but also legal frameworks, such as human rights legislation.

Overview of existing laws regarding AI/CCAM

Ensuring the compliance of AI-based CCAM with relevant laws and regulations is crucial for the development of such technologies, but even more so in building public trust towards it. The development of lawful AI-based CCAM systems is an ongoing field of research and development, with new laws and regulations being enacted or modified to accommodate technological advancements and changing needs. Therefore, compliance with legal and ethical considerations of any AI-based CCAM development should be regularly reviewed. The next subsection includes non-exhaustive overview of international regulations and standards related to the development and implementation of CCAM technologies in the automotive sector, together with a selection of references to national regulations for the same sector.

International regulations and standards

At the global level, international organisations such as the United Nations or the **International Organization for Standardization (ISO)** are developing global standards and guidelines for CCAM. Given the fast pace of development of regulations in the field, several initiatives are attempting to provide overviews of the most recent trends in that direction. Two examples are Holistic AI (2023) and the [ConnectedAutomatedDriving.eu](https://connectedautomateddriving.eu) initiative. Holistic AI publishes a yearly review of global AI regulations. In the [2023 edition](#), Holistic AI recognised four global leaders in the AI regulatory ecosystem: the EU, the USA, the UK and China. The [ConnectedAutomatedDriving.eu](https://connectedautomateddriving.eu) initiative has a dedicated section of its website on [regulation and policies](#), where the result of the projects (such as ARCADE) focusing on standards and guidelines relating to automated vehicles are listed. In the following subsections, some of the international regulations and standards currently employed in relation to CCAM is summarised as follows:

¹ The term “ethical” is explicitly mentioned here to indicate that we do not rely on a simplistic concept of legality. Codified law may grant legality to new technologies, but it does not make them inherently ethical. Conversely, ethics exist outside of legal frameworks and therefore merit separate mention.

Non-EU laws and regulations

At the international level, organisations like the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) and ISO have played significant roles in developing regulations and guidelines related to AI and CCAM. Table 1 presents a concise overview with some core examples.

Table 1. Overview of current international regulations, standards and guidelines for CCAM initiatives (non-exhaustive)

Organization	Regulation / standard / initiative	Short description and link
United Nations	Multi stakeholder high level Advisory Board on AI undertaking analysis and recommendations for international governance of AI.	Interim report on Governing AI for Humanity identifying principles to guide the formation of new global AI governance institutions. Interim Report: Governing AI for Humanity
	Resolution on steering AI towards faster realisation of sustainable development	Resolution to bridge AI and other digital divides considering inter-and intra-country perspectives to promote safe, secure and trustworthy AI systems Document A/78/L.49
United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE)	UNECE WP.1 Global Forum for Road Traffic Safety	Platform for countries to exchange knowledge and best practices related to CCAM, promotes the development of international standards. Road Traffic Safety UNECE
	UNECE WP.29 Regulations	Regulations specific to automated driving systems that cover various aspects such as vehicle safety, cybersecurity, and data access. Vehicle Regulations UNECE
International Organization for Standardization (ISO)	ISO 22737:2021	Guidelines for the development and testing of AI systems used in automated vehicle systems. ISO 22737:2021
	ISO 21448 (SOTIF)	Safety of the Intended Functionality (SOTIF) standard focuses on the identification and mitigation of hazards related to the intended functionality of AI systems in vehicles. ISO 21448:2022
International Telecommunication Union (ITU)	ITU-T Focus Group on AI for Autonomous and Assisted Driving	Develop technical standards and guidelines for AI applications in autonomous and assisted driving Focus Group on AI for autonomous and assisted driving (FG-AI4AD) (itu.int)
OECD	AI Principles	OECD AI Policy observatory and principles The OECD Artificial Intelligence Policy Observatory https://www.oecd.org/going-digital/ai/principles/

EU laws and regulations

The European Commission has been actively working on the preparation of on-road testing and pre-deployment activities of CCAM. In [2018](#) the EC announced its intention to “establish a single EU-wide platform grouping all relevant public and private stakeholders to coordinate open road testing of Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) and make the link with pre-deployment activities”. The platform brought together over 400 public and private experts, organised in six thematic working groups. The [report](#) of this expert group is publicly available but to date, their recommendations have not been adopted as formal legislation in the EU. The directions of these new pieces of legislation touch upon connected roads, cooperative ITS (Intelligent Transport Systems, unified databases, standardised testing rules, EU-wide C-ITS security credential management system (EU CCMS), cooperation on cross-border testing of CCAM, and others.

Several legislations have been adopted at EU level regarding the development of AI and CCAM. The laws presented in Table 2 are currently the most relevant ones in the EU, as reflected in the knowledge base of the CAD project and the Holistic AI (2023) yearly review of global AI regulations.

Table 2. CCAM-related legislation and guidelines in the European Union

Type of law / regulation	Regulation / standard / initiative and link	Short description
Approval frameworks	Directive 2007/46/EC (2007)	Article 20 specifies the requirements for type-approval exemptions for new technologies or concepts which allows Member States to grant an EC type-approval. The approval is for new technologies or concepts that don't comply with certain regulations in Annex IV, Part I of the Directive. Manufacturers can apply for this exemption, which may result in a temporary approval valid within the issuing Member State.
	Regulation (EU) 2018/858, amending Regulations (EC) No 715/2007 and (EC) No 595/2009 and repealing Directive 2007/46/EC.	Approval and market surveillance of motor vehicles and their trailers, and of systems, components and separate technical units intended for such vehicles.
	Regulation (EC) No 78/2009	Type-approval of motor vehicles regarding the protection of pedestrians and other vulnerable road users.
General Regulation	EU AI Act 2021/0106 (COD) (REF , 2022) –adopted in spring 2024	EU law on artificial intelligence (AI) that assigns applications of AI to three risk categories: 1) applications and systems that create an unacceptable risk; 2) high-risk applications are subject to specific legal requirements; 3) applications not explicitly banned or listed as high-risk are largely left unregulated. (REF , 2023)
	EU Digital Markets Act (DMA) - Regulation (EU) 2022/1925 (REF) and EU Digital Services Act (DSA) - Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 (REF , 2022)	The DSA and the DMA form a single set of rules that apply across the whole EU. They have two main goals: 1) to create a safer digital space in which the fundamental rights of all users of digital services are protected. 2) to establish a level playing field to foster innovation, growth, and competitiveness, both in the European Single Market and globally.
	Regulation (EC) No 661/2009 (REF)	Type-approval requirements for the general safety of motor vehicles, their trailers and systems, components and separate technical units intended therefor.

Connectivity / C-ITS	Directive 2010/40/EU (REF)	Framework for the deployment of ITS in the field of road transport and for interfaces with other modes of transport.
Privacy & data protection	Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR) (REF)	Protection of persons regarding the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation). It includes data collected by CCAM systems.
	ISO 21448 (SOTIF) (REF)	Safety of the Intended Functionality standard focuses on the identification and mitigation of hazards related to the intended functionality of AI systems in vehicles.
Guidelines	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI https://ethicsstandards.org/repository/	Key principles and ethical considerations for the development and deployment of AI, including AI-based CCAM systems.
	Ethics of CAVs: recommendations on road safety, privacy, fairness, explainability and responsibility (Report)	Promote a safe and responsible transition to CAVs by supporting stakeholders in the systematic inclusion of ethical considerations in the development and regulation of CAVs.
	Guidelines on Automated Individual Decision Making and Profiling for the Purposes of Regulation 2016/679 (Source , 2018)	Covers general and specific provisions on profiling and automated decision-making, children and profiling, data protection impact assessments and data protection officers.

National regulations

Many countries are developing and updating their regulations for the development, testing, and deployment of CCAM vehicles. Although some collections of overviews exist (e.g. CAD initiative) none is comprehensive and, given the fast pace of development in the field, this would be unrealistic to expect. Therefore, a selection of examples from countries where CCAM-related regulations have been introduced is presented, with at least one representative example per continent (if available). Table 3 provides an overview of the current CCAM-related legislation in the selected nine countries.

Table 3. Representative CCAM-related legislation in countries around the world

Country	Law name	Description
USA	Federal Automated Vehicles Policy (2016)	Guidance and policy framework for the testing and deployment of automated vehicles in the United States. It includes a 15-point safety assessment and encourages voluntary cooperation between industry stakeholders and regulators.
	AV START Act (pending legislation)	Aims to establish a federal regulatory framework for autonomous vehicles, including provisions related to safety, cybersecurity, and data privacy.
	National Highway Traffic Safety Administration (NHTSA) Guidelines	Guidelines for automated driving systems, addressing safety, cybersecurity, and data privacy.
Germany	Autonomous Driving Act (2022) KBA	Legal framework for autonomous driving in Germany. It includes provisions related to driver responsibilities, liability, data protection, and insurance requirements for AVs.
United Kingdom	Code of Practice for Automated Vehicle Trialling (2015)	Offers guidance for trialling and testing automated vehicles on public roads in the UK. It covers safety, insurance, data protection, and cybersecurity considerations.

Code of Practice		
Singapore	Autonomous Vehicles Act (2017) Road Traffic (Autonomous Motor Vehicles) Rules 2017	Establishes a legal framework for the testing and deployment of AVs in Singapore. It includes provisions related to safety standards, cybersecurity, and liability.
China	Road Traffic Safety Law (2011) Law of the People's Republic of China on Road Traffic Safety - China.org.cn	Provides a legal basis for AV testing and deployment in China. It includes provisions related to road safety, liability, and licensing requirements for AVs.
Chile	Autonomous Vehicle Law (2020)	Chile enacted its AV Law to provide a regulatory framework for AV testing and operation on public roads. The law covers aspects such as vehicle requirements, testing permits, insurance, and liability.
Australia	Guidelines for Trials of Automated Vehicles in Australia (2017)	Framework for conducting trials of automated vehicles on Australian roads. They cover aspects such as safety, insurance, and data management.
United Arab Emirates (UAE)	Dubai Autonomous Transportation Strategy (2016)	Initiative to transform 25% of transportation in Dubai into autonomous mode by 2030. This strategy involves the development of necessary regulations and infrastructure to support CCAM.
	Federal Traffic Law (2024)	Includes amendments to vehicle classifications including modern advancements in technology. The new law adapts to increasing use of self-driving vehicles and electric cars.

The regulations are emerging at a different pace in countries and regions around the world. In general, South American and African countries have limited legislation focused on CCAM. This is true for most developing countries, due to a combination of factors, including the absence of a domestic AV industry, limited investment capacity in the technology, and deficient infrastructure to maintain consistent internet/network connectivity (Shahedi 2023).

Human rights in relation to the concept of lawful AI-based CCAM

The human rights perspective in lawful AI-based CCAM emphasises the universal need to protect and promote the fundamental rights of individuals in the context of the development and deployment of AI-based automated transportation systems. By embracing the human rights framework, the discussion surrounding lawful AI-based CCAM strives to ensure that technological advancements in this field serve the best interests of individuals and communities.

Most research on the topics of law and ethics in AI, including CCAM or AV technologies, agree on a core set of principles that need to be accounted for to address any potential human rights risks and violations. These are the right to: human dignity, self-determination and liberty, life and security, protection of personal data, equality and non-discrimination as well as explanation. Mechanisms to ensure these rights include human agency and oversight, the use of metrics for human, societal and environmental well-being, and transparency and accountability mechanisms (AI HLEG 2018, EC 2020, Lütge 2021, IEEE). According to the European Commission's High Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, "AI systems should hence be developed in a manner that respects, serves and protects humans' physical and mental integrity, personal and cultural sense of identity, and satisfaction of their essential needs." (AI HLEG, 2019). Refer to Annex II, for the overview of these core principles with brief explanation of their meanings.

Legal gaps

While significant progress has been made in developing international laws and standards related to AI and CCAM, several legal gaps still exist. These gaps reflect the challenges posed by the rapid advancement of AI technologies and their integration into CCAM systems. Human-centred legal gaps that need to be addressed focus mainly on safeguarding human rights, ensuring accountability and promoting the wellbeing of individuals in relation to AI and CCAM systems.

Some of the key human-centred legal gaps in CCAM & AI include:

- **Data protection and privacy** – Non-EU countries lack robust measures akin to GDPR, leaving gaps in safeguarding personal data rights.
- **Bias and discrimination** - Legal gaps exist in addressing biases that may arise from training data or algorithmic decision-making processes. There is a need for legal frameworks to ensure fairness, accountability, and transparency in AI algorithms to prevent discriminatory outcomes.
- **Transparency and explainability** – A uniform legal framework is absent, which is necessary for individuals to understand and challenge AI system decisions.
- **User consent and control** – No standardized rules exist regarding user consent, data collection limits, and the ability to opt out or modify settings, hindering user control.
- **Accountability** – Legal mechanisms are essential to clarify the responsibilities and liabilities of stakeholders in the event of accidents or failures involving AI-based CCAM systems.
- **Standardisation and alignment of regulations** – Different jurisdictions have varied legal approaches, hindering interoperability and cross-border operations, complicating AI and CCAM system development.
- **Legal provisions for upcoming levels of automation** - The lack of specific regulations for Level 4 and Level 5 automation leaves critical aspects like testing, liability, safety standards, and ethical considerations unaddressed (ERTRAC 2022).
- **Human-machine collaboration and trust** – Legal frameworks need to define roles, responsibilities, and ethical considerations for human-machine collaboration in CCAM. They should address **human oversight**, decision delegation, and mechanisms to maintain user trust and confidence in AI systems.

Addressing these human-centred legal gaps requires a multidisciplinary approach involving legal experts, policymakers, ethicists, and stakeholders from various domains. It involves the development and implementation of legal frameworks that prioritise human rights, fairness, transparency, and accountability, ensuring that AI and CCAM systems serve the best interests of individuals and society.

1.2.2 Ethics

Balancing privacy, fairness, and safety in AI requires careful consideration and trade-offs to mitigate ethical risks and promote responsible innovation. This balance is achieved through interdisciplinary collaboration among engineers, policymakers, and stakeholders, coupled with early ethical analyses. Responsible innovation aligns with "value-sensitive design," embedding values into design through ethical analysis and guidelines to address value conflicts (Santoni de Sio, 2016). The "Responsible Research and Innovation Approach" (RRI) enhances this by emphasizing inclusiveness (through societal dialogue), anticipation (of benefits and risks), reflexivity (by being explicit about societal challenges due to technology), and responsiveness (through experimentation and adaptation) (EPRS, 2022). These frameworks link human-centric AI with ethical considerations in CCAM applications.

Research on machine ethics has identified key ethical concerns:

1. Intrinsic ethical issues (e.g., moral dilemmas, value pluralism),
2. System failure and corruptibility risks (e.g., incorrect inputs, complex cases, bad actors).

3. Risk of creating “moral patients” (i.e., machines that are granted moral agency are treated as subjects deserving moral considerations and obligations, conflicting with human control),
4. Unequal distribution of benefits (i.e., who benefits from AI technology), and
5. Moral responsibility and accountability (e.g., **automation paradox** i.e., automated machines tend to (1) compensate for human incompetence, (2) erode existing human skills, and (3) fail in situations that are likely to catch humans off-guard and ill-prepared) (Jansen et al., 2019).

AI also presents specific ethical challenges in daily life:

1. Privacy, surveillance, and behavioural manipulation.
2. Transparency and explainability.
3. Bias and discrimination.

AI-driven robotic devices raise additional concerns:

4. Meaningful human control.
5. Employment and the future of work.

Autonomous vehicles (AVs) pose unique ethical issues:

6. safety,
7. newly distributed obligations, responsibilities, and liability in traffic systems, and
8. data proliferation and associated privacy concerns, power imbalances, and the privatisation of public spaces.

These ethical concerns are dynamic and likely to evolve over time, such as the future energy use of AI bringing sustainability into focus. This uncertainty presents opportunities for ethics research to detect new ethical issues introduced by technological advances (EPRS, 2022). The thematic clusters of ethical concerns listed above also reaffirm the need to extend the discussion beyond ethical dilemmas faced by autonomous vehicles alone. Instead, it bears repeating that the methodology proposed here calls for a broader approach, including system-level ethics. In the following sections, the current state of ethical considerations and risks for AI-based CCAM is introduced, followed by a synthesis of guidelines aimed at supporting developers and implementers of the technology.

Proposed ethical frameworks – then and now

AI challenges existing norms and introduces new risks, frequently described as ethical concerns. Since ethics is a universal field with a long history, there is no shortage of theoretical models for ethics in AI (the [AI Ethics Guidelines Global Inventory](#) included 167 contributions in 2020). Early research on AI-based CCAM focused on hypothetical scenarios involving specific ethical dilemmas, thereby posing ethical questions primarily in terms of liability and data processing (Pillath, 2016). These scenarios like the “**trolley problem**” (with MIT’s [Moral Machine](#) (active from 2016 to 2020)) are criticised for limited utility due to unrealistic expectations of AV challenges (Tolmeijer et al., 2024).

Recent research adopts a syncretic approach² to balance moral requirements and public acceptance. aiming to align theory with practice and policy as AV technology evolves and regulatory demands increase. Ethical Valence Theory (EVT) addresses moral uncertainty and the lack of consensus by describing AV decision-making as claim mitigation, offering stakeholders flexible options based on environmental information and empirical research (Evans et al., 2020). Similarly, the **agent-deed-consequence (ADC)** model evaluates moral judgments through intuitive assessments of the agent, deed, and consequence, recognizing bad actors but considering mitigating circumstances. This model critiques the trolley problem and **utilitarianism**, which might justify “selfish AVs” as instruments with limited financial or legal liability that prioritize passengers regardless of other factors. In turn, the ADC allows for mitigating circumstances to determine what is morally acceptable, for instance when an action generally perceived as negative (i.e., breaking a law) was motivated by good intentions and had a positive outcome (i.e., avoidance of harm or damage) (Dubljevic 2020).

² combining or bringing together different philosophical, religious, or cultural principles and practices

The naturalistic ethics approach contributes to the debate by acknowledging the influence of dynamic socio-cultural environments on moral decisions. This approach has practical implications for the global regulatory landscape of AVs, encouraging the harmonization of national laws while allowing cultural perspectives to shape national parameters. AV manufacturers could offer a range of ethical policies, and buyers could select insurance policies that reflect their moral attitudes. The naturalistic framework encompasses a wide spectrum of agents in ethical decision-making, indicating their level of responsibility for AV behaviour (Arfini et al., 2022).

The frameworks presented here do not provide a comprehensive picture of the AV ethics universe, and the field has its limitations. Recent studies identify a gap between theory and practice in AI ethics research, advocating for a meta framework to address deficiencies in:

1. Embedded ethics approaches (susceptible to biases).
2. Ethically aligned approaches (risk of incomplete justification theories).
3. **Value Sensitive Design (VSD)** (potential blind spots in political, legal, or social governance) (Bleher and Braun, 2023).

Embedded ethics approaches are susceptible to the introduction of biases due to the vagueness and subjectivity that is inherent in professional judgments. Furthermore, such biases can be amplified by underlying (and unacknowledged) power structures in research settings, bringing questions of diversity, **equity** and inclusion into play. In contrast, ethically aligned approaches tend to emphasise principles as high-level, top-down guidance for the implementation of AI ethics. The prescriptive nature of this process reveals a potential weakness in the form of incomplete or non-existent justification theories to explain trade-offs between competing principles. Finally, the VSD approach promises to define ethical values throughout the entire (technological) design process with the intention of identifying and resolving ethical conflicts among stakeholders as early as possible. Like the previously discussed approach, this can become problematic if justifications for certain value choices are underdetermined. In addition, an overly rigid focus on the design process risks creating blind spots or missing linkages to political, legal, or social governance aspects. These observations call for adding analytical dimensions:

- 1) Visibility of biases, power structures, and marginalization in AI ethics research by including the dimension of affects and emotions.
- 2) Strong justification theories for resolving ethical conflicts to provide standards and guidance on whether and how to prioritise certain principles.
- 3) Consideration of governance dimensions in ethical AI development (Bleher and Braun, 2023). Arguably, this point could be seen as self-evident in an EU-funded research project such as AITHENA, but it bears repeating considering proposed holistic methodology.

Ethical principles play a prominent role in policy-oriented documents but need comprehensive approaches to address the complexities of AI and AV ethics. The proposed methodology aims for a holistic approach, considering technical, social, legal, and political processes in developing ethical AI.

Ethical Principles

Recent research on AV ethics reveals a lack of consensus on prioritizing ethical principles or how to label them. One study emphasizes “minimizing human injury, preventing casualties and non-discrimination based on gender, age, race or other factors” constitute the primary goals “of all ethical notions in vehicle autonomy” (Madhav and Tyagi, 2023). Other highlights minimizing overall risk, prioritizing the worst-off, ensuring equal treatment, responsibility, and maximum acceptable risk (Geisslinger et al. 2023). Some researchers acknowledge the difficulty of achieving universal ethics guidelines and suggest focusing on what is considered unacceptable or potentially unlawful (Tolmeijer et al. 2024). The table below synthesizes guidelines relevant to EU policymaking, identifying recurrent principles and publications that can serve as ethical AI checklists (also including summarised principles/requirements in Annex II). The discussion that follows outlines gaps and unresolved ethical issues needing further research. The aim is to develop a methodology that links ethical principles (“the ‘what’ of AI ethics”) to practical implementation (“the ‘how’”) (Morley et al., 2019).

Table 4: Synthesis of the guidelines for ethical principles in AI (table format adapted from Hagendorff, 2020)

Synthesis of Guidelines for Ethical Principles in AI (table format adapted from Hagendorff, 2020)								
	CPAIS 2019	IEEE 2019	Turing 2019	EC AI HILEG 2019	EC Ethics of CAVs 2020	UNESCO 2021	AI4People 2021	OECD 2022
Title	"Human - AI Collaboration: Key Insights from a Multidisciplinary Review of Trust Literature"	"Ethically Aligned Design: A Vision for Prioritizing Human Well-being with Autonomous and Intelligent Systems"	"Understanding artificial intelligence ethics and safety: A guide for the responsible design and implementation of AI systems in the public sector"	"Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI"	"Ethics of Connected and Automated Vehicles: Recommendations on road safety, privacy, fairness, explainability and responsibility"	"Recommendation on the ethics of artificial intelligence"	"AI4People: Ethical Guidelines for the Automotive Sector - Fundamental Requirements and Practical Recommendations"	"Recommendation of the Council on Artificial Intelligence"
Author(s)	Partnership on AI (PAI)/ Collaborations Between People and AI Systems (CPAIS) Expert Group	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) Global Initiative on Ethics of Autonomous and Intelligent Systems	David Leslie/The Alan Turing Institute	European Commission High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence	Horizon 2020 Commission Expert Group to advise on specific ethical issues raised by driverless mobility	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO)	Luetge et al./AI4People Automotive Committee	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)
Key issue/main argument/stated goal of publication	"Understanding trust between humans and AI systems is integral to promoting the development and deployment of socially beneficial and responsible AI."	"establish societal and policy guidelines in order for intelligent systems (A/IS) to serve humanity's values and ethical principles. These systems must be developed and operate to benefit people and the environment, beyond simply reaching functional goals and addressing technical problems. This approach will foster the trust between people and technology that is needed for its fruitful use in our daily lives."	"This document provides end-to-end guidance on how to apply principles of AI ethics and safety to the design and implementation of algorithmic systems in the public sector."	"The aim of the Guidelines is to promote Trustworthy AI."	"aims to promote a safe and responsible transition to connected and automated vehicles (CAVs) by supporting stakeholders in the systematic inclusion of ethical considerations in the development and regulation of CAVs."	"approaches AI ethics as a systematic normative reflection, based on a holistic, comprehensive, multicultural and evolving framework of interdependent values, principles and actions that can guide societies in dealing responsibly with the known and unknown impacts of AI technologies on human beings, societies and the environment and ecosystems, and offers them a basis to accept or reject AI technologies."	"advise [...] on specific ethical issues that arise from autonomous vehicles (AVs)." "provide the automotive sector, including both companies and public entities such as regulators, with concrete and practical guidelines to comply with ethical principles within the AI systems of AVs."	"aims to foster innovation and trust in AI by promoting the responsible stewardship of trustworthy AI while ensuring respect for human rights and democratic values." "focuses on AI-specific issues and sets a standard that is implementable and sufficiently flexible to stand the test of time in this rapidly evolving field."
Affiliation (academia, govt., industry, NGO)	Academia, Industry, NGO	NGO	Academia, NGO	Government	Government	Government	Academia, Govt., Industry, NGO	Government

Identified gaps

The synthesis of guidelines highlights the relevance of principles like fairness, well-being, and transparency. However, even with consensus on prioritizing ethical issues, challenges remain. Firstly, **guidelines alone do not make principles operational or explain how they can be incorporated into system designs**. This gap necessitates further research and the development of specific tools and techniques (Prem, 2023). Checklists for ethical AI design, testing, and implementation are one such tool, explicitly mentioned in three of the guidelines analysed.

Secondly, **determining responsibility for implementing ethical AI is complex**. AI is a field with high degrees of uncertainty as well as technical and social complexity, shaped by the following characteristics: “(1) AI is built on assumptions; (2) human behaviour is complex; (3) algorithms can have unfair consequences; (4) algorithmic predictions can be hard to interpret; (5) trade-offs are usually inevitable; and (6) positive, ethical features are open to progressive increase, i.e., an algorithm can be increasingly fair, and fairer than another algorithm or a previous version, but it makes no sense to say that it is fair or unfair in absolute terms” (Morley et al., 2019). This list suggests that multi-disciplinary approaches are necessary for the creation of ethical AI applications. Collaborations among engineers, philosophers, and policy specialists are crucial to ensure products reflect public values. Diverse teams throughout the AI production process also mitigate risks, ensuring ethical principles are maintained from design to deployment (Morley et al., 2019).

Lastly, **governance challenges** include democratic controls and enforcement. Ethical principles alone are insufficient; they must be enforceable. Only two of the eight documents analysed refer to inclusive deliberation and multi-stakeholder governance. The private sector's reliance on self-governance can undermine public oversight. Additional barriers include profit motives, lack of ethics training, weak organizational structures, and representation issues, as AI research and ethics discourse remain male-dominated (Hagendorff, 2020).

1.2.3 Robustness

The requirement of robustness is linked to the principle of harm prevention, which impacts user acceptance (EC JRC, 2022). Robustness has a social and technical dimension. “**Socially robust**” refers to the “due consideration of the context and environment in which the system operates” (EC AI HLEG, 2019a), while robustness from a technical perspective implies “ensuring the system’s technical robustness as appropriate in a given context, such as the application domain or life cycle phase” (EC AI HLEG, 2019b). Technical robustness also refers to the “ability of an AI tool or algorithm “to maintain its performance and accuracy under expected or unexpected variations in the input data” (Future AI, 2023).

When exploring the topic of AI robustness in current literature, we observe a strong inclination to cover only its technical dimension. Even in the JRC report on “Robustness and Explainability of Artificial Intelligence” (Hamon et al., 2020), the social aspects are explored from the perspective of environmental and societal well-being rather than robustness. The concept of socially robust AI is explored here highlighting its close relation to other core topics of trustworthy AI, such as fairness, accountability, or privacy.

Socially robust AI

A first exploration of existing literature using the term “socially robust AI” yields very few results. This leads us to believe that the concept is only starting to gain acceptance now that technically robust guidelines have been established and validated. Starting from the definition offered by the AI HLEG given above, we can examine the potential components of socially robust AI as understood from the syntagm of “consideration of the context and environment”. Elements that can influence the social robustness of an AI system include Legality, Culture, Fairness, Subjective perception, and Social awareness (AI for social good).

Technically robust AI

According to the High-Level Expert Group on AI (2019b), the technical robustness of an AI algorithm “requires that AI systems be developed with a preventative approach to risks and in a manner such that they reliably behave as intended while minimising unintentional and unexpected harm and preventing unacceptable harm. This should also apply to potential changes in their operating environment or the presence of other agents (human and artificial) that may interact with the system in an adversarial manner. In addition, the physical and mental integrity of humans should be ensured” (EC AI HLEG, 2019). According to the same publication, the technical robustness involves ensuring that the AI system is:

- Secure and resilient to attacks - the AI system is protected against vulnerabilities that can allow them to be exploited by adversaries, e.g., hacking.
- Accurate - ensure the ability to make correct judgements and predictions (e.g., correctly classifying information into the proper categories)
- Reliable and reproducible – ensure that the system works properly with a range of inputs and in a range of situations (reliable), and that it describes whether an AI experiment exhibits the same behaviour when repeated under the same conditions (reproducible).

This narrow focus has significant implications for how developers and testers should approach the design and evaluation of (sub-)systems. As AITHENA has proposed in the technical architecture outlined in the figure below, the project looks at accuracy and robustness per sub-system, creating pragmatic checklists for developers and testers to verify these aspects. Since the accuracy of one sub-system affects the subsequent sub-system, it also dictates the robustness requirements for the following stages. Therefore, it is essential to define accuracy levels for each sub-system and establish boundary conditions for when a subsequent sub-system is considered robust.

High-accuracy scores can be misleading if the model performs well on majority classes but poorly on rare classes, which might be crucial for the task. Thus, selecting the right metrics is paramount for a trustworthy evaluation of model performance. These metrics should be explained and openly communicated, especially when showing poor performance on specific aspects.

In AV behaviour planning, accuracy involves adhering to desired, reasonable driving behaviours. Algorithms can produce various outputs: high-level decisions like accelerating or overtaking, or explicit trajectories with spatial and temporal data. For trajectory-based methods, metrics such as the average **Mahalanobis distance** (in conjunction with other metrics) to a ground-truth trajectory are useful for evaluation. High-level decision outputs, however, require comparative metrics for subjective behavioural classifications. Defining desired driving behaviour is complex due to its subjective nature and varying assessments, influenced by regional, social, and manufacturer-specific

preferences. To address these diverse requirements, evaluation criteria should be divided into hard and soft categories: soft criteria are assessed by the vehicle manufacturer or developer, while hard criteria should be verified by regulatory authorities for function approval.

Figure 4: Technical architecture of the AITHENA project

Key lessons

All levels of the pipeline (perception, situational awareness, decision making, traffic management) require different metrics for accuracy and robustness. Accuracy and robustness on the traffic management level (AI for CCAM) is (typically) less clearly defined. Errors from earlier systems cascade into later systems, lowering overall robustness. Links between metrics are not always clearly defined.

The complexity of robustness at the traffic management level is highest due to scale of operation, interaction with other traffic and infrastructure, dynamically changing environments and use of communication (delays, failure, errors) with clear definition and terminology of ODD (e.g., SOTIF).

2. EVALUATING FAIRNESS IN AI-BASED CCAM APPLICATIONS

Fairness in autonomous transportation systems is crucial for establishing trust and aligning with societal norms and values (Mehrabi et al., 2021). However, achieving fairness is complex and context-dependent, with challenges arising from both algorithmic and human-driven practices (Holstein and Dodig-Crnkovic, 2018). While algorithmic fairness addresses bias and discrimination in automated decisions, a socio-technical perspective acknowledges the interplay between social and technical elements in achieving fairness (Dolata et al., 2022). The adoption of connected and cooperative autonomous mobility (CCAM) systems presents an opportunity to rectify existing transportation inequalities, such as inequitable access to public transport and unequal road space distribution but requires careful consideration and regulatory guidance to ensure fairness (Pfeiffer et al., 2023).

In the EU context, **fairness** is implicit in the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights but **is not explicitly mentioned in the AI Act**, highlighting the need for more explicit references to fairness in AI legislation to ensure trustworthy AI (Binns, 2021). This chapter addresses fairness from both technical and societal perspectives, exploring common technical definitions such as non-discrimination and unbiasedness, as well as broader societal notions like equality and **procedural fairness** (Binns, 2021). By providing insights into determining appropriate definitions of fairness and anticipating potential harms from unfair designs, this chapter aims to guide stakeholders in the CCAM development process.

Recent research has shifted towards considering broader decision processes in AI fairness, emphasising societal fairness components like **equality, non-discrimination, and procedural fairness** as essential elements of human-centric design. While there's a tendency to focus on quantifying discrimination and bias, there's an increasing recognition of the importance of **distributive fairness**, including equality (Dolata et al., 2022; Pfeiffer et al., 2023). Non-discrimination analysis aims to prevent systematic favouritism or discrimination based on sensitive attributes, particularly in domains like recruiting and credit, where AI algorithms can exacerbate wealth disparities (Kordzadeh and Ghasemaghahi, 2021; Pfeiffer et al., 2023). Procedural fairness involves decision-making processes and accountability, with societal fairness perspectives yielding conflicting evaluations of fairness. Some recent examples of unfair representation in AI include: biased prediction of criminal recidivism based on race in the case of the COMPAS dataset (Angwin et al., 2016); or the presence of racial bias in a widely used health algorithm in the USA (Obermeyer et al., 2019).

The following fairness checklist (and parallel ones in subsequent chapters) is intended to guide your reading through the chapter. The reader is encouraged to consider how he/she would answer the questions for his/her own project. While a quantitative response is not possible in every case, each checklist question is intended to prompt reflection among developers of AI-based CCAM functions. Each question also links directly to a paragraph in the chapter which provides examples and/or references for further reading on the topic to help the reader consider the relevant aspects of fairness.

2.1 Fairness checklist

Topic and question		Target group(s)
SAFETY	Does your AI algorithm include an intentional situational awareness function/feature?	Developer, Auditor, Authorities
	What provisions for the safety of vulnerable road user groups are taken by your application?	Developer
	How is the AI algorithm you are designing equipped to manage dilemmas? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Risk distribution based on estimations of harm (e.g., for AVs: considering speed, angle of collision, and type of road users involved in a collision) Considering shared ethical principles Other 	Developer, Authorities
ACCESSIBLE AND UNIVERSAL DESIGN	What provisions for ensuring Universal Design did you make for your AI algorithm?	Developer
	What type of data collection methods are you using? Have you evaluated the robustness of your collection methods and data storage?	Developer
	Are other road users able to communicate or interact with the autonomous vehicles (e.g., to negotiate road crossing)?	Developer, Authorities
	Do the human-computer interactions of the traffic management system consider the needs of road users in wheelchairs, who are blind, or who are deaf?	Developer
PROCEDURAL FAIRNESS	Which stakeholder groups have you involved in the development and testing phases? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> developers distributors operators clients regulators users CCAM specific: local public transport authorities CCAM specific: transportation planning agencies Other 	Developer, Authorities
	What processes have you established for encouraging and supporting diverse ways of thinking in relation to the identification of bias, non-discrimination, and unwanted societal impact of your AI algorithm? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Inclusion of diverse staff Inclusion of various professional/cultural backgrounds Inclusion of people with different physical abilities Inclusion of social positions Others 	Developer, Authorities
	Is your data prone to any of the following user-to-data types of bias: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Historical bias 	Developer

BIAS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> b) Population bias c) Self-selection bias d) Social bias e) Behavioural bias f) Temporal bias g) Content production bias 	
	<p>Is your AI algorithm prone to any of the following data-to-algorithm types of bias:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Measurement bias b) Omitted-variable bias c) Aggregation bias d) Sampling bias e) Linking bias f) Longitudinal data fallacy 	Developer
	<p>Is your AI algorithm prone to any of the following algorithm-to-user types of bias:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Algorithmic bias b) User-interaction bias c) Popularity bias d) Emergent bias e) Evaluation bias 	Developer
NON-DISCRIMINATION	<p>Does the AI application use datasets that represent people? If not, how else could the performance of the AI model be related to human values?</p>	Developer
	<p>Who are the stakeholders in the use case and which of them are most vulnerable?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Cyclists b) Pedestrians c) People with reduced mobility d) Other 	Developer, Authorities
	<p>How might the characteristics of the test data differ depending on different definitions of fairness?</p>	Developer
	<p>Is it feasible and appropriate given privacy commitments to collect the data required to calculate a fairness test?</p>	Developer
	<p>If considering group fairness metrics, is it possible to classify the people represented in the data in protected and unprotected groups?</p>	Developer
	<p>Which groups could be identified/ affected/connected to your AI algorithm?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Groups b) Subgroup user-interaction bias c) Individuals d) Other 	Developer, Authorities
	<p>Are you employing disaggregated evaluations (i.e., assessing performances separately for different demographic groups) to uncover performance disparities?</p>	Developer, Authorities
	<p>Do you use fairness metrics for the testing and optimisation of your model?</p>	Developer

2.2 Societal Fairness

The following subsections go deeper into the components of societal fairness in AI and explore how sources of unfairness present in CCAM systems relate to societal notions of fairness.

2.2.1 Equality

The concept that people should be treated equally is a core component of fairness in society. Yet, like fairness, there is no clear objective regarding exactly what should be equalised across people, such as **equal opportunity** or equal distribution of goods, and whether such a rule should remain consistent across different contexts (Binns, 2021). Further, to what extent should redistribution occur and under what circumstances? Depending on the chosen objective, the resulting policy may align more closely with the concept of equity than equality, where equity considers how people may require differential treatment to reach the same outcome. For example, a family with young children require different accommodations than elderly travellers when using transportation systems. Current recommendations related to CCAM systems and equality focus on four themes. The first three are well-established topics in transportation planning and the fourth has emerged specifically in the context of AI-enabled CCAM. These include 1) safety provisions, 2) transport accessibility, 3) accessible design, and 4) open data access. These topics coincide with the main benefits that automated mobility systems promise; thus, this section discusses how these benefits can be distributed fairly.

2.2.2 Safety

Variations of the *trolley problem* dominated early discussions on autonomous vehicles and ethics as the opportunity to automate decisions within such difficult situations posed new ethical concerns. Despite these ethical dilemmas, the promise of improved safety is a major driving force for AV development. More recently, AV experts have tried to move past the dilemma discussion and toward a broader focus on how these safety improvements are distributed. Further research is needed to determine the technical details of these suggestions and how they affect the development process of CCAM systems.

The Horizon 2020 Commission Expert Group that authored “Ethics of Connected and Autonomous Vehicles” (2020) recommend that autonomous vehicles redress the inequality of vulnerability among road users so that “no category of road user (e.g., pedestrians, cyclists, motorbike users, vehicle passengers) should end up being more at risk of harm from CAVs than they would be against this same [current] benchmark.” They specify that this is not equivalent to “observing an average decrease in harm” since **the distribution of harm and safety could be distributed unequally across types of road users**. Implementing this recommendation affects the development of the CCAM system via intentional situational awareness that is sensitive to perceived vulnerabilities of road users. It also affects vehicles’ decision making, obliging them to provide extra space or to drive at lower speeds around vulnerable groups.

The Expert Group report also recommends that vehicle decision making should aim to manage dilemmas by principles of risk distribution and shared ethical principles (Horizon 2020 Commission Expert Group, 2020). They write, “Rather than defining the desired outcome of every possible dilemma, it considers that the behaviour of a CAV in a dilemma situation is by default acceptable if the CAV has, during the full sequence that led to the crash, complied with all the major ethical and

legal principles [...] and if there were no reasonable and practicable preceding actions that would have prevented the emergence of the dilemma.” A similar approach was developed by Geißlinger et al. (2022) who designed **an algorithm that equally distributes risk across road users based on estimations of harm considering speed, angle of collision, and type of road users involved in a collision**. The approach does not distinguish between types of physical harm or deathly outcomes; rather, it assumes that the severity of the physical harm is universally proportional to the external factors of the vehicle kinematics and impact area. It is not clear how the algorithm incorporates the possibility of a vehicle travelling with multiple passengers into the objective to minimise estimated harm. Nonetheless, this is a particularly important area for future research because thoughtful solutions would also address the “trolley problem”, along with related dilemmas that dominate the discussion of ethics and autonomous vehicles. Whereas recommendations, such as those from the EU Expert Group, tend to assume there is some level of shared understanding/validity for concepts such as vulnerability, risk distribution, proportionality and harm minimisation, this is not necessarily the case.

2.2.3 Transport Accessibility

Connected and cooperative autonomous mobility systems promise greater transport accessibility, where transport accessibility measures the ease or opportunity to reach a desired location. Essentially, more people can reach the places they need to go. Autonomous vehicles can expand transport access particularly for people who cannot currently operate a vehicle by themselves, either because of physical or cognitive disabilities. Similarly, the possibility of reduced congestion would also increase accessibility for all travellers. To achieve an increase in accessibility for everyone, the new service models in CCAM systems must not discriminate in service provision based on ability to pay or frequency of use (e.g., by using an algorithm that makes a service more easily available in high-end neighbourhoods by providing more vehicles in the area, reducing the accessibility in deprioritised neighbourhoods). The report “Ethics of Connected and Autonomous Vehicles” (Horizon 2020 Commission Expert Group) notes how this **discriminatory service could manifest as “different individuals or groups of users receiving: (a) unequal access to products or services; (b) discriminatory forms and quality of service such as reprioritisation, deprioritisation, and even denial of access to products and services in periods of high demand; and (c) discriminatory differential pricing strategies for CAV access.”** Developers and product providers of AI applications related to vehicle routing, fleet management, and traffic management must adopt a conscious strategy to avoid **algorithmic bias** that would jeopardise this aspect of fairness.

2.2.4 Accessible and Universal Design

Unlocking the benefits of the CCAM system for the community of people with reduced mobility requires the adoption of universal design in all human-computer interactions. The seven principles of universal design ensure that anyone, regardless of age, language spoken, presence of a disability, etc. can equally use and participate in the system. These principles (see: <https://www.udinstitute.org/principles>) are:

- 1) Equitable use
- 2) Flexibility in use
- 3) Simple and intuitive use
- 4) Perceptible information
- 5) Tolerance for error
- 6) Low physical effort
- 7) Size and space for approach and use

Applied to autonomous vehicles, this requires intentional efforts beyond the physical design of vehicles, but also within the user interface and design for vehicle users, communication methods with nearby road users, and the efforts to make AI decision making transparent (Costa et al., 2018). Following the ethics guidelines written by the EU High-Level Expert Group on AI, Lütge et al. (2021) also note how “levels of differing abilities need to be acknowledged (e.g., a young individual may have quicker reflexes for executing requests than elderly people) and the **systems need to be adapted accordingly for different users, so that everyone can benefit from this new technology**”.

For AI processes related to perception and situational awareness, designers and developers need to consider how user input is collected and whether different types of collection methods are available and equally robust. Similarly, in traffic management systems, how are other road users able to communicate or interact with autonomous vehicles to negotiate road crossings (or other driving manoeuvres near each other)? Do these expected ways of communicating incorporate non-verbal or communication in multiple languages? **Do the human-computer interactions of the traffic management system consider the needs of users in wheelchairs or of those who are blind or deaf at road crossings?** Without intentional human-computer interaction, access to these emerging technologies will be unequal, unfair, and reinforce existing inequalities.

2.2.5 Open Data

Open data represents an emerging focus area within fairness and transportation as it forms a critical infrastructural component of emerging CCAM systems with higher demands for public access than is practised in current transportation systems. The task of regulating access to important datasets for auditing and safety purposes supports efforts in transparency and is counterbalanced by data privacy protections. Moreover, as evidenced in other technology-driven sectors, open access to data – or the lack thereof – is associated with other instances of (un)fairness related to non-discrimination. The report on Ethics of Connected and Autonomous Vehicles states, “open, free and equal access to information – in the sense of informational infrastructures and raw material for knowledge and innovation – constitutes a requirement for fair market competition, consumer empowerment, transparency and accountability in the shared interest of citizens, consumers, industry and states” (Horizon 2020 Commission Expert Group 2020). Therefore, **developers, auditors, and policymakers should work to identify high-value datasets that should be protected as public resources as well as datasets that would improve CCAM system development and safety if shared across stakeholders**. These include data on AV behaviour in dilemma situations and traffic management failures.

2.2.6 Procedural fairness

Procedural fairness in AI involves transparent decision-making processes (see also Chapter 5), with this section delving into defining, evaluating, and remedying fairness in AI. Key considerations include determining the definition of fairness, overseeing its implementation, conducting audits, and rectifying any identified unfairness. To enhance stakeholder engagement, AI practitioners can use previous efforts, such as surveys and collaborate with communication and participatory design experts, to gather extensive input. Surveys on public perceptions and expectations of autonomous vehicles, such as those outlined in the recent literature review “Promoting Community Readiness and Uptake” (2022), serve as valuable references. Notably, **while many surveys focus on autonomous vehicles, there's a gap in research regarding connected and cooperative autonomous mobility systems**, highlighting the need for future studies to ensure effective implementation of cooperative traffic management systems.

Pfeiffer et al. (2023) outline five main stakeholder groups: developers, distributors, operators, clients, and regulators. From these, teams should solicit feedback with special attention paid to final users. In the context of AI-based CCAM, local public transport authorities and transportation planning agencies are additional groups as operators and clients that could have feedback related to defining and evaluating fairness in the local context. When engaging directly with affected communities, **“it is important to be wary about extractive, tokenistic approaches which can unfairly burden members of marginalized groups”** (Madaio et al. 2022). Inclusive deliberation through public engagement and educational programmes is especially important for sensitive topics such as criteria for navigating dilemma-based safety situations (Horizon 2020 Commission Expert Group, 2020).

Fairness in AI must encapsulate the public's normative views, although pinpointing these views for every context is highly challenging (Pfeiffer et al., 2023; Madaio et al., 2022; AI High-Level Expert Group, 2018). This suggests that AI practitioners begin with personal and empathetic perspectives, acknowledging the limitations of this approach due to the lack of diversity within many AI teams across ethnicity, religion, gender, and other value-informing identities. The inclusion of diverse backgrounds is crucial for recognising and addressing the spectrum of potential injustices, emphasising the **importance of diverse hiring practices and the support for varied ways of thinking to achieve fair AI outcomes**. Additionally, procedural fairness is highlighted, underscoring the need for mechanisms that allow individuals to contest and seek compensation against AI decisions, as well as transparent documentation and accountability in decision-making processes. This multifaceted approach to fairness emphasises both the composition of AI teams and the procedural safeguards as essential components in fostering equitable AI applications.

2.3 Technical considerations in ensuring fairness

“A technological intervention to which the Fairness Principle applies is morally right only if it does not lead to unfair inequalities in society” (Peterson 2017). From that viewpoint, the concept of fairness is closely linked both to the principle of non-discrimination from a technical perspective and to the above discussion on societal aspects.

Algorithmic fairness becomes particularly important when considering machine learning algorithms, as they learn from historical data that may already contain biases. If a machine learning algorithm consistently makes unfair decisions, it can perpetuate systematic discrimination because it is likely to influence a significant number of future cases (Pfeiffer et al., 2023). The figure below provides an overview of the essential elements in ensuring fairness in AI algorithms.

Figure 5: Overview of essential elements in ensuring fairness in AI algorithms (adapted from: Cheng et al. 2021)

2.3.1 Bias

Bias originated in statistical studies but is now pervasive across disciplines, particularly in psychology. It denotes systematic errors in perception and judgment. **When human bias infiltrates AI through data or algorithms, its impact is intensified, stemming from the need for rapid information categorisation.** This bias, whether from flawed assumptions in algorithm development or inherent biases in training data, carries grave consequences for crucial decision-making realms. Addressing AI bias mandates stringent testing of data and algorithms, alongside the construction of diverse, representative systems fostering ethical, human-centred design principles to gain user trust. **Recognising the multifaceted sources of bias, including human behaviour, skewed assumptions, or training data artifacts, is pivotal.** The legal, ethical, reputational, and functional risks posed by AI bias underline the imperative to acknowledge and mitigate it in research. Efforts to identify, understand, measure and mitigate bias remain central in AI development – although they are unable to eradicate it entirely. More than 200 cognitive biases have been identified (Cirillo & Rementeria

2022) that can potentially influence machine learning model design. Mehrabi et al. (2021) highlights the cross-disciplinary nature of bias, categorising it into user-to-data, data-to-algorithm, and algorithm-to-user biases, illustrating the complex interplay between human cognition, data processing, and algorithmic decision-making. Table 5 provides examples of how each of these biases can be manifested in CCAM development.

Table 5: Bias definitions and examples in CCAM development

Type	Name	Description (Mehrabi et al. 2021)	Example in CCAM development
User to data bias	Historical bias	A result of existing biases and socio-technical issues in the world. Can influence the data generation process, even if sampling and feature selection has been done perfectly.	An AI traffic prediction model trained on data from a city with a history of underinvestment in certain neighbourhoods may perpetuate existing biases in resource allocation.
	Population bias	When statistics, demographics, representatives, and user characteristics on the platform differ from the original target population. It leads to non-representative data.	The variation in user demographics across navigation apps, with certain apps being more popular among given demographics.
	Self-selection bias	When research subjects voluntarily choose to participate, leading to a biased sample.	In a survey measuring satisfaction with a transportation service, the most satisfied users may be more likely to respond, skewing the results.
	Social bias	This occurs when others' actions and behaviours influence our judgment.	Reviewing a transportation service with a low score but changing our evaluation influenced by other high ratings, assuming we might be too severe.
	Behavioural bias	Variations in user behaviours across different context or datasets.	Differences in route preferences among users can result in inaccurate traffic predictions.
	Temporal bias	Differences in populations and behaviours over time.	A traffic prediction model trained on data from a specific time may not accurately reflect changes in traffic patterns over time.
	Content production bias	Structural, lexical, semantic, and syntactic differences in the contents generated by users.	Variations in language use across different cultures can introduce biases in the generated content.
Data to algorithm bias	Measurement bias	Arises from how we choose, utilize, and measure features. Measurement bias can occur because of certain intrinsic habits of people capturing data such as poorly trained survey trained interviewers. Another source of measurement bias could be a result of the device used to capture dataset (e.g., Poor quality images captured by camera).	Measurement bias could arise from inaccurate sensor readings or inconsistent data collection methods across different vehicles.
	Omitted variable bias	When important variables are left out of the model (Wilms, 2021) because the data is not available, it is difficult to obtain, researchers are not aware of the importance, or intentionally left out due to concerns about the correlation of several independent variables.	OVB could occur if important variables, such as road conditions, traffic patterns, or weather, are not included in the model. This could lead to incorrect conclusions about the behaviour of CCAM systems and their impact on traffic flow, safety, and efficiency.
	Aggregation bias	Occurs when false conclusions are drawn about individual behaviour or characteristics based on observations made at the group level (Jargowsky, 2005) leading to incorrect conclusions about individual behaviours or characteristics. Also known as ecological fallacy.	Aggregation bias can arise when data from urban environments with well-developed infrastructure is combined with data from rural areas with limited connectivity. If a CCAM system is trained on this mixed data, it may underperform in rural settings because the data predominantly reflects urban conditions. This can result in an overemphasis on urban scenarios in the decision-making processes of autonomous vehicles, leading to difficulties in rural areas where road conditions, traffic patterns, and connectivity differ significantly.
	Sampling bias	Arises due to non-random sampling of subgroups and is one of the most common types of dataset bias. Sampling bias can imply trends estimated for one population may not generalize to data collected from a new population.	Sampling bias in CCAM research can lead to limitations in the generalizability of trends and safety benefits observed in a city to other cities or populations with different characteristics, infrastructure, or adoption rates of CCAM technologies.

	Linking bias	The uncorrected representation of user behaviour and network attributes obtained from user connections, activities, or interactions. This bias can arise when only considering the links in the network without considering the content and behaviour of users. It can lead to skewed perceptions and biased observations about users.	Linking bias can arise in the analysis of traffic patterns and congestion level based only on network links without considering the behaviour of individual drivers.
	Longitudinal data fallacy	The incorrect analysis of temporal data using cross-sectional analysis instead of longitudinal analysis, which can lead to biased conclusions	A study examining the adoption rate of connected and autonomous vehicles (CAVs) may find that Region A has a higher adoption rate than Region B based on a single point in time. However, a longitudinal analysis tracking the same regions over time may reveal that Region B experienced a higher growth rate in CAV adoption.
Algorithm to user bias	Algorithmic bias	There are biases that are introduced by the algorithm itself and are not inherent in the input data. These biases can arise from design choices made in the algorithm, such as the use of specific optimisation functions or regularisation techniques.	An algorithm employed for traffic signal optimization might prioritize certain routes over others, resulting in an unfair allocation of green signal time and disadvantaging specific groups of commuters
	User interaction bias	User interaction biases are present in user interactions and, in general, in user behaviour, which can be influenced by both the user interface and the user's own biased behaviour. This bias can manifest in different forms, such as presentation bias, which occurs when the way information is presented influences user choices.	In a connected vehicle navigator, if some routes are prominently suggested to users, ranking bias occurs, as users tend to click on the most ranked result, assuming they are the most relevant.
	Popularity bias	Popularity bias emerges when certain items receive more attention or preference, due to their high popularity. It is important to recognise that popularity metrics could be manipulated.	This type of bias can occur when certain routes or services are given more exposure or preference based on their popularity.
	Emergent bias	Emergent bias occurs as a result of real-world use and interaction with users. This bias arises because of a change in population, in cultural values, or in societal knowledge that emerges after completion of the system design	UI in CCAM systems is very susceptible to emergent bias, as they are designed to align with characteristics, capacities, and habits of users. Thus, a shift in context of use may well create difficulties for a new set of users. This type of bias can be divided into more subtypes (Friedman, 1996).
	Evaluation bias	Evaluation bias occurs when model evaluation is influenced by inappropriate benchmarks.	Evaluation bias can occur during the evaluation of the models being used for applications such as facial recognition and traffic prediction.

Figure 6: Sources of bias in systems (source: Brown et al., 2021)

2.3.2 Non-discrimination

Non-discrimination is legally required by the EU Charter on Fundamental Rights and by legislation of Member States. [Article 21](#) of the EU Charter on Fundamental Rights establishes that "any discrimination based on any ground such as sex, race, colour, ethnic or social origin, genetic features, language, religion or belief, political or any other opinion, membership of a national minority, property, birth, disability, age or sexual orientation shall be prohibited." National and local transportation agencies involved in implementing and managing CCAM systems are subject to this standard as public bodies of EU Member States. Private enterprises involved in CCAM development in the EU are subject to less restrictive non-discrimination directives related to race and gender in the context of employment access and access to goods and services, though many Member States require higher standards. Moreover, the non-discrimination directives are broad and context dependent in court (Wachter, 2021). There is no universally satisfying technical definition of fairness. Algorithmic decision making differs from human decision making in scale, complexity, and speed, and discriminated categories may not align with any socially meaningful groups, like those listed in Article 21. In transportation systems, meaningful groups vary based on travel patterns and reasons, with individuals often switching between different modes of transport in a single day.

In addressing fairness in AI, the focus often lies on mitigating discrimination, a concept which is distinct, yet difficult to separate, from bias within socio-technical systems. Mehrabi et al. (2021) categorise discrimination as prejudice based on sensitive attributes, while bias in AI refers to discriminatory outcomes stemming from data or algorithms. Although eliminating discrimination is crucial, achieving fair outcomes extends beyond this, involving the assessment of differential impacts across all use cases, even in AI applications not directly dealing with human data. Furthermore, in the context of CCAM systems and broader AI applications, it's vital to consider the vulnerability of different stakeholder groups, including those historically marginalised or physically vulnerable, such as cyclists, pedestrians, and individuals with reduced mobility. This comprehensive approach underscores the **necessity of considering both the legal and societal implications of discrimination and the importance of tailoring technical tools to identify and protect vulnerable groups within various systems**. This should emphasise a holistic view of fairness that encompasses both bias mitigation and the protection of vulnerable stakeholders.

While discrimination can manifest as disparate treatment or impact, statistical fairness metrics often prioritise testing for disparate impact, which implies disparate treatment. However, disparate treatment isn't always unfair, as seen in gender quotas for business and political representation. Machine learning models aim to categorise data for accurate predictions, yet human involvement can introduce discriminatory biases. Statistical fairness metrics fall into three categories: group, subgroup, and individual fairness. These evaluate outcomes across demographic groups, smaller subgroups, and individuals with similar characteristics, respectively (Narayanan, 2018). Fair ML research focuses on translating these concepts into numerical measures, primarily addressing group fairness metrics (Hutchison and Mitchell, 2018). For further details and techniques on fairness measures and mitigation, see Mehrabi et al. (2021). The table below presents technical fairness definitions and categorisations from Mehrabi et al. (2021).

Table 6: Technical definitions of fairness

<i>Name</i>	<i>Description (from Mehrabi et al. 2021)</i>	<i>Group</i>	<i>Subgroup</i>	<i>Individual</i>
Demographic parity	The chance of being assigned a positive outcome is the same regardless of which group a person belongs to.	X		
Conditional statistical parity	People in protected and unprotected groups have equal probability of being assigned a positive outcome given a set of related factors.	X		
Equalised odds	Both protected and unprotected groups should have equal rates of being correctly assigned a positive outcome (true positive) and being incorrectly assigned a positive outcome (false positive).	X		
Equal opportunity	Protected and unprotected groups should have the same rate of being correctly assigned a positive outcome (true positive rate).	X		
Treatment equality	The ratio of incorrect negative assignments to incorrect positive assignments is the same for both protected and unprotected groups.	X		
Test fairness	For any value of a predicted probability score, the protected and unprotected groups have equal probability of being correctly assigned to the positive class (true positive rate).	X		
Subgroup fairness	Identifies a group fairness metric and applies this test to a collection of subgroups.		X	
Fairness through unawareness	No protected attributes are used in the decision-making process.			X
Fairness through awareness	Similar individuals (measured by inverse distance metric) receive similar outcomes.			X
Counterfactual fairness	An individual receives the same outcome with their actual characteristics as when they (counterfactually) belong to another demographic group.			X

These concepts are important tools for defining fairness, measuring those definitions, and mitigating elements of unfairness using Fair ML. Yet, Fair ML metrics alone do not sufficiently operationalise fairness and can generate additional challenges for data scientists. A naive approach would be to try to optimise the AI algorithm across as many measures as possible or across a select few metrics that are thought to be particularly important. However, “as can be seen in the different notions, **there is no universal operationalization of fairness; further, it is mathematically impossible to fulfil all the different notions**” (Dolata et al., 2022). For example, if the prevalence rate of the event in question differs between the protected and unprotected groups in the testing data, it is impossible to optimise all the metrics within the group fairness category. Thus, developers and auditors must be intentionally selective of the definitions of fairness that they wish to apply based on the context of the AI application.

How does one choose the most appropriate definition of fairness that ensures non-discrimination given the context? There are several factors that should be considered and that can be identified through stakeholder analysis and by reflecting on data requirements and availability. First, **if the AI application uses data that represents individuals or people, the opportunities for unfairness are much greater**. Nonetheless, practitioners working on applications that do not require datasets representing people should consider how the outcomes of their product are related to human values and different definitions of fairness.

Second, **practitioners should identify the major stakeholder groups connected to the use case and consider how their different perspectives might lead to different definitions of fairness.** For example, in the context of traffic management systems, transportation engineers might understand fairness in terms of efficiency, while transportation planners might understand fairness in terms of overall safety, and individuals consider fairness in terms of their ability to get to their destination without considerable challenges.

In considering stakeholder groups, AI teams should aim to identify groups or subgroups that are the most vulnerable. Considering the historical and social context of transportation systems and mobility solutions is an important step for identifying vulnerable stakeholder groups. Within CCAM systems, an obvious group with high vulnerability are less protected road users such as cyclists and pedestrians (associated as VRUs, i.e., Vulnerable Road Users). Within those groups, people with reduced mobility who use walking aids or wheelchairs or are travelling with young children are particularly vulnerable.

As most of these fairness definitions require additional data for testing, AI practitioners need to investigate whether collecting this type of additional data is consistent with commitments to data privacy. Similarly, teams must consider whether existing datasets offer appropriate comparisons as the target group of users may represent only a portion of what is captured by population level statistics. For instance, in testing perception applications for their ability to correctly identify people with different physical attributes (e.g., wheelchair users), local conditions, including sidewalk ramps, sidewalk quality, and overall density greatly affect the rate of encountering those certain groups. Thus, the appropriate proportion of wheelchair users in a testing dataset depends on the local context in which it will be employed. Moreover, **many categories used to identify groups of people are difficult to impose in practice as common classifications do not reflect the complicated reality of personal identities.** People with mixed race or ethnic backgrounds, hidden or unique disabilities, or fluid gender identities do not neatly fit into existing classifications. Imposing inaccurate labels could cause further harm through obfuscation. Finally, AI practitioners must investigate how other data features used in the AI application may act as proxy data for protected characteristics. This is especially important when measuring fairness through unawareness³. Additional considerations or recommendations emerge specifically for the four use cases in the AITHENA project. The table below provides an example of some of the ethical questions that need to be addressed at different “stages” of CCAM (perception, situational awareness and decision making) as well as considerations that must be taken in traffic management systems – using the example of the AITHENA use cases.

³ These considerations were drawn from the following sources, where additional guidance can be found: the Preamble to Microsoft’s AI Fairness Checklist (Madaio et al., 2020), Shari Trewin’s essay on AI Fairness for People with Disabilities (2018), Reuben Binns’ article *Fairness in Machine Learning: Lessons from Political Philosophy* (2018).

Table 7: Considerations associated with prioritised aspects per AITHENA use case

Use case priority aspect	Associated considerations
Perception (AITHENA use case 1)	Are sensors able to identify people with different physical characteristics equally well within and across different datasets? How is "equally well" defined? Are these aspects addressed through the model and/or data-cards being developed?
Situational awareness (AITHENA use cases 2.1 and 2.2)	As the AI models obtain information from images or other raw data from sensors, and produce detected events, how are the annotations of the recorded data certified and validated to ensure the ground-truth i.e., situational awareness? For instance, to identify situations of interest (which can be less frequent) how is the content (that is not representative) filtered out and how does it affect the accuracy of the situational awareness?
	Generating motion predictions in a complex urban environment should cater to numerous interactions between different traffic participants and road infrastructure elements, including information on traffic regulations and road users that are less protected (e.g., pedestrians, cyclists, people with reduced mobility).
Decision making (AITHENA use case 3)	There is consensus across several ethics groups that manufacturers must not consider physical characteristics of nearby road users as factors in vehicle manoeuvre decisions (Horizon 2020 Commission Expert Group, 2020; Holstein and Dodig-Crnkovic, 2018). In addition, considering that the decision making is data driven how strongly does it influence the behaviour of the autonomous vehicle? What considerations are taken to make sure that training data or lack of data does not pose any challenge in a real-world scenario for the AV and other road users?
Traffic management systems (AITHENA use case 4)	How is priority determined for road users that are not using autonomous vehicles? How will routes or vehicle priority be decided in automated traffic management using AI?

2.4 Tools

Achieving fairness in autonomous systems involves navigating contextual determinants and employing best practices and tools for bias mitigation and discrimination avoidance. Brown et al. (2021) offers a four-step approach for mitigating bias in datasets, emphasising exploratory data analysis, establishing population benchmarks, independent ethics board validation (if available), and data disclosure. Mehrabi et al. (2021) provides techniques for bias mitigation across major AI algorithms.

Disaggregated evaluation, as advocated by Barocas et al. (2021), reveals disparities by calculating robustness and performance metrics for different groups, addressing hidden biases. However, **reducing performance disparities while maintaining fairness metrics can be challenging.** Practitioners must specify the appropriate fairness metric and apply pre-processing, in-processing, or post-processing techniques accordingly (John-Mathews et al., 2022).

Fair ML techniques aim to integrate corrective measures into machine learning methods. Several Fair ML tools have emerged in the past decade, supporting fairness exploration and evaluation. Table 8 lists complementary tools adopting holistic fairness definitions. **To ensure effectiveness, diverse teams should employ these tools alongside stakeholder engagement and auditing processes** (Section 2.2).

Table 8: Fair ML Tools

Tool	Description and link
FairLearn	Accessible tutorial that walks through the relevant concepts related to fairness in AI and provides technical examples with sample code. https://fairlearn.org/

Microsoft AI Fairness Checklist	Thorough outline of how fairness should be considered in all steps of product development and deployment. https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/project/ai-fairness-checklist/
FairSight	Pipeline to examine fairness at each step in ML workflow with a dashboard for visualizing the process. https://github.com/ayong8/FairSight#readme
AI Fairness 360	Comprehensive resource with tutorials for data scientists and open-source algorithms for mitigating bias in AI. https://github.com/Trusted-AI/AIF360

2.5 Challenges and gaps for further research

The academic literature on algorithmic unfairness mainly focuses on established sensitive categories like gender or race, but **ongoing exploration is crucial to uncover non-apparent biases**. Realist Fairness Engineering acknowledges inherent biases in our social structures and emphasises considering real-world factors in AI development (John-Mathews et al., 2022). Data operations are influenced by power relations in the social world (Crawford & Calo, 2016; Eubanks, 2017; John-Mathews et al., 2022), **challenging the notion of achieving fairness solely by following rules**. Perfect fairness may not always be feasible due to data limitations, algorithm complexity, and competing objectives (John-Mathews et al., 2022).

Alignment between methodology and practitioners' workflows is a key implementation challenge, potentially leading to harmful outcomes in bias identification and fairness pathways (Madaio et al., 2022). Fairness perception is context sensitive and subject to individual interpretation. Pfeiffer et al. (2023) stress the importance of democratic debate in addressing biased choices and institutions, **advocating for ongoing reassessment of sociotechnical systems to prevent lock-in effects** (D21, 2020).

3. EVALUATING TRANSPARENCY IN AI-BASED CCAM APPLICATIONS

This chapter provides a **checklist** and a set of **guidelines** that any developer, manufacturer or authority may consult in terms of what defines a transparent artificial intelligence (AI) or machine learning (ML) solution and what associated **transparency criteria** a proposed or already existing model fulfils and which not. It also presents basic concepts used in the field of **explainable AI** (XAI).

The vast and ever-growing field of machine learning applications is entering every aspect of technology, from household items such as vacuum robots that contain simple ML solutions to highly complex industrial applications, and automated driving is not exempt from this development. Indeed, it heavily – and in some cases solely – depends on the use of artificial intelligence or Machine Learning systems to drive tasks that seemed nearly impossible even a decade ago. These tasks range from object detection, where the autonomous vehicle assesses its surroundings and classifies objects around it (houses, people, the street, trees, traffic lights, etc.) (e.g., Fujiyoshi et al., 2019; Caeser et al., 2020; Cai et al., 2021) over route and trajectory planning (Aradi, 2020), to risk assessment (Li et al., 2022; Shi et al., 2020) involving the safety of the vehicle, the occupants, and other traffic participants in the environment.

As with every technology, ML models are not flawless in carrying out given tasks. Their performance depends on many different parameters, including the data that was used to train them, their architecture and their capability to generalise (and perform well) tasks they were not explicitly trained on.

Many applications, especially those using deep-learning-based approaches (Bell et al., 2022), perform well and are efficient in what they do (i.e., task solving) but their inner workings are completely untransparent (e.g., how they classify an object; what leads to a given decision, etc.). This does not pose serious problems in areas that can tolerate mistakes, even critical ones. These mistakes may reduce the measured performance of the model, but not have dire consequences.

In safety-critical fields such as medicine (Setz et al., 2021) or, as in the AITHENA project, autonomous driving (Zablocki et al. 2022), a model must make many critical decisions such as forecasts, classifications, etc. If the model shows erroneous behaviour, the need for an explanation in these cases is real and important. Explanations allow us to find the source of the ML model's behaviour, assess how likely it is that the faulty behaviour will occur again, and yield clues on how the application could be improved to avoid the same mistake in the future.

The checklists below (and related guidance) can be used in assessing whether an AI model conforms with the important transparency criteria known to the field of XAI – either for planning an AI model that will perform its tasks transparently or for authorities to check for transparency capabilities in a proposed AI model. All questions should be answered to get an overview of the transparency criteria applied to every AI model in a project.

How transparent a model must be, again, depends on the given task. If it is used in non-critical conditions or for less important tasks and one does not feel the need to understand a model's behaviour, an untransparent model can be a good option, as efforts to create transparency consume effort and time. A good example would be a model trained to recognise handwritten numbers and letters. As long as it performs well, the few mistakes it makes are easily tolerable. In this case there is no real need for explanations (even if this could be interesting).

The need for transparency is given when the task is safety critical or involves a decision with serious impacts and consequences, as is the case with autonomous vehicles. Each task should therefore be weighted in accordance with the consequence it can carry for the user (harm, liability, financial decisions, etc.). The level of transparency needed can be derived from the seriousness of the task. The question should always be: "If mistakes occur in AI decision making, what are the consequences if the mistakes persist and are not understood?" If the answer to this is anything but: "These mistakes can easily be tolerated", then XAI techniques are necessary for the analysis of your AI model.

3.1 Transparency checklist

Feature ranking	Audience
Ranking of all qualitatively different features according to their importance for the model performance	All
Ranking shows percentual importance for every feature	All
Importance ranking was cross evaluated	All
Input highlighting	
Highlighting of important input data patterns/pixels/motifs when data is presented visually (images, graphs, etc.)	All
Different input highlighting methods are evaluated for uniformity of yield explanations	All
Validity of salient patterns/pixels/ motifs is evaluated by strategies (e.g. insertion or deletion testing)	All

Neuron importance	Audience
A general assessment of importance for every single neuron was performed	Dev
An importance assessment for specific input classes/categories was performed for every single neuron	Dev
Task success evaluation	
An analysis was performed of how well each subtask of an AI model was solved	All
Model metrics evaluation	
A set of metrics was chosen and then tested to ensure the set is appropriate and complete to evaluate the given task	All
All chosen metrics are depicted numerically and with their given confidence interval	All
There are clear metrics in place to measure resistance to interference/attacks.	All
Which metrics to use for accuracy?	All

Data quality and uncertainty are addressed in the AI development process.	All
There are certification standards/procedures in place to be followed.	All
Computational intensity	
Computational load/effort to train and perform inference with a given model and dataset is depicted.	All
Assessment of whether computational requirements enable/hinder the use of the AI model for certain uses (e.g. real-time live applications) as inference times are short enough/too long	All

Data representation	Audience
Samples are evaluated for even distribution amongst different classes/phenomena	Dev/Auth
In cases of imbalanced datasets, data weaknesses are well documented and discussed	Dev/Auth
Data collection and quality	
In case of biases, these are documented and discussed	All
Data collection procedures are documented	All
Data processing conditions are documented	All
People/institutions involved in data collection/processing are documented	All
Data was collected under unbiased conditions	All
In case of biases, these are documented and discussed	All

Presentation of information	Audience
Information is easily visible/perceivable to potential users.	All
Only the most relevant information is presented in time-sensitive surroundings/ situations (e.g., while riding in an autonomous vehicle).	All
Information presented is optimised not to overwhelm users with too much sensory information.	All
Information presented is refined and easily understandable (and tested to be so) for various users (young, elderly, low/high education, etc.).	All
Insights are presented in a user-group appropriate way:	
○ For developers/manufacturers	All
○ For end users	All
○ For authorities	All

3.2 Basic concepts of transparency and explainable AI (XAI)

3.2.1 Transparency

In its literal meaning, transparency describes the property of a substance to let light pass through it, therefore allowing a spectator a view through an object made of this substance and see what lies behind it (see Cambridge University Press, n.d.: “the characteristic of being easy to see through”). The term transparency is strongly associated and even sometimes used interchangeably with the terms explainability and interpretability (Lipton et al., 2018). In the field of machine learning, transparency is understood in different ways in different contexts, but it always aims in a direction of how easy it is to understand the inner workings and decision-making processes of a machine learning model (Larsson et al., 2020). Combining this simple view and modern interpretations of transparency in the field of AI, we try to define a useful understanding of transparency in relation to AI.

On the level of machine learning models (Larsson et al., 2020), transparency refers to insights into the inner workings of the model itself and the importance of the input data regarding a given task. It also encompasses transparent communication of insights from the model to diverse user groups.

Figure 7: Four aspects of transparent AI (and examples of each)

3.2.2 The explanation paradigm

Before going into the different avenues of transparency, some general concepts in the field of XAI are defined for clearer understanding. The key terms in understanding transparent, explainable AI are “object”, “observation”, “interpretation” and “explanation”.

Figure 8: General concepts in explainable AI

Every **object** in the world has properties that describe its nature (e.g., height, weight, colour, etc.). In the case of autonomous driving, some typical relevant objects are streets, cars, people or trees.

Using sensors, a set of object properties can be measured and described as data points (a camera measures images in terms of pixel intensities; a scale measures weight, etc.). This is called an **observation**. The properties that can be measured depend solely on the available sensors. Typical sensors in autonomous driving are lidar, cameras and radar, which are used to describe objects in their surroundings.

Using observational data and oftentimes additional information, such as (human-made) labels or categories associated with the data, a machine-learning algorithm can carry out a given task. A task could be to classify measured image material (pedestrians, cars, traffic lights, etc.), or to make a prediction (e.g., future trajectories of traffic participants around the autonomous vehicle). This process uses the machine learning system to associate meaning to measured observational data and is called an **interpretation**.

With interpretations made by machine-learning algorithms, it is often unclear how the models came to a specific result. All methods and approaches that try to produce insights into which part of the model is relevant for a certain result (model-specific explanations) or which data is relevant for a certain result (input-specific explanations) are called explainable AI (XAI) methods. They offer **explanations** for a model’s decisions which are of varying degrees of usefulness. Typical explanations for machine-learning tasks in autonomous driving are to determine which visual characteristics of pedestrians are required (e.g., visible head, minimum height, etc.) to classify them as a human, rather than as a car, a dog, a tree or something else.

3.3 Explainability methodology

3.3.1 Explainable AI (XAI) methods

Any method designed to increase the number of insights into an AI model is called an explainable AI (XAI) model or method. There is a vast and growing number of such methods that explore a variety of avenues to make an AI model's decision understandable for an outside observer. These methods aim to increase transparency regarding either the model or input level, with transparency related issues discussed in Section 3.4. They also try to create explanations for the AI model's behaviour on either a local scale (trying to explain classifications on single samples for example) or on a global scale (trying to illuminate how the model reaches conclusions in a more generalised way).

3.3.2 White and black box models

In the field of machine learning, AI models can be roughly categorised into two classes with respect to how easy their decisions are to understand and to explain. Black-box models use self-learned complex mathematical functions (e.g., deep-learning approaches) or complex representation spaces to achieve goals like predictions or classifications on given datasets. While achieving great performance in a vast variety of tasks, their inner workings and how they come to a given decision/outcome are inherently opaque and not interpretable even for experts in the field. (Larsson et al., 2020). This is because these models do not offer any human-understandable (i.e., rule-based) approach to solving a task. They are a complex function approximator trained for efficiency, but not for **understandability**.

White-box models, by contrast, are more pattern and rule-based (e. g. Random Forest models) (Larsson et al., 2020). They can solve many of the same tasks as black-box models, although with worse performance in many cases. They are interpretable by experts, and even by laypeople in some cases (Larsson et al., 2020).

3.3.3 Black-box models and *post-hoc* explanations

Black-box models are used frequently due to their higher level of task performance than white box models. Many methods have been developed in recent years to make them transparent to a certain degree, introducing so-called *post-hoc* models to explain decisions made by a trained black-box model. These explanations are provided after a decision has been taken by the black-box-model (Slack et al., 2021).

Post-hoc models or methods differ in terms of what the generated explanations look like, what the models highlight, which black-box models they are suitable for, the computational resources they need and, most important, whether they provide local or global explanations about a black-box model.

Local explanations are those that try to explain a model's decision when confronted with a single example of a task, for example to classify one specific image. A local explanation could try to highlight feature importance, highlight areas of the images that are relevant for the classification or show those parts of the model that are most relevant for the classification (neuron groups for example) (Setzu et al., 2021).

Global explanations do not focus on a single example but try to describe how a black-box model comes to a decision in general. By either generalising local explanations to a higher level, for example giving feature importance over a whole set of samples instead of single ones (Setzu et al., 2021), some **XAI methods** or models even try to formulate global rules that the ML model follows, such as: *"If the image shown contains a red or green object and its contours are roundish, there is a high probability that it is an apple."*

3.3.4 Human-understandable explanations

In the field of machine learning, an artificial intelligence model is presented with observations and a task, which together, define the whole world the AI has any knowledge about. This limits the number of interpretations it can perform on a given dataset. For example, if a machine learning model has learnt to differentiate between apples and pears and had never been given any classification options other than these, the model has only two possible interpretations of any given observation. This means it would, for lack of any other options, have to classify a tomato as either an apple or a pear.

By contrast, humans can refer to a near infinite amount of conceptual knowledge and types of classes taken from a lifetime of experience. This illustrates the large gap between a human and a machine learning model with a task. If the ML model is "asked" to provide an explanation of its interpretation, it could only refer to its limited knowledge. Any explanation would therefore have to aim to bridge this gap by providing enough meaningful information for a human to understand a ML model's limited interpretation.

3.4 Meaningful insight into AI models

What is a meaningful insight into a machine learning model? What are informational qualities that lead to a better understanding of a decision or prediction made by artificial intelligence? The following subchapters look at these transparency-related issues at different levels around every ML model.

3.4.1 Transparency of input

ML models take an input (an image, set of data points, etc.), perform operations on it and come to an interpretation (classification, prediction, etc.) of the given input observations. If the model offers an explanation of the interpretation, it can be about the input data and is very often highly valuable.

Assuming an image, the model could highlight parts of the images that are crucial for the classification as a specific object. Assuming tabular data like a patient's weight, height, age, blood cholesterol, etc., the model could make predictions about the patient's risk to develop specific illnesses and create a ranking of the most important factors in the tabular data that lead to this decision. This kind of explanatory behaviour is often called **feature** (or **input**) **importance** and selects parts of the input that were important for the model to create an interpretation.

Feature importance

Given a set of features (e.g., dimensions, colours, reflectivity of an object), the explainability method allows one to determine the importance of every feature – for example hierarchically from most to least important – for a given machine learning task. Methods ranking importance can be susceptible to an effect where features are tested one after another and one feature is deemed important if it is sufficient to solve a task. If the task can be solved sufficiently well, the following features are deemed unimportant even if they had a similar importance if they were tested earlier (before the other

features). This effect can be alleviated by cross evaluation, i.e., testing importance multiple times with only a partial feature set or a different order of tested features.

Input highlighting

Given optically interpretable input (e.g., image, time series data), one should highlight the data points that are most relevant for the given machine learning task, such as object detection or classification. Typical methods include saliency-map-based methods, showing the most relevant pixels in an image needed for image classification. Different methods may deem different data points important. Highlighted; multiple testing runs with different highlighting methods, can yield an overview of the possible spread of highlighted data points. Highlighted data points can also be tested for their task-specific relevance (i.e., how important were they really to solve a given task?), by so called insertion or deletion methods (Petsiuk et al., 2018).

3.4.2 Model transparency

ML models have varying architectures but generally consist of many neural network layers that perform mathematical operations on a given input to yield a meaningful interpretation as an output.

Identifying most important neurons for a task

Models that can select or highlight single neurons or specific sets of neurons that are important for an interpretation can use this neuron-highlighting as an explanation for their behaviour. In image classification, the model could highlight a set of neurons that are responsible for apple detection, and no other fruits. This highlighting of model-internal decision-making structures can shed light on erroneous behaviour that is otherwise not understood.

A model tasked with classifying different fruit species could perform poorly on apples. Seeing the responsible neurons, an ML expert could analyse the responsible neurons and search for strategies to improve their behaviour to enhance the model's capability to classify apples.

Subtask performance evaluation

Given a machine learning model with several subtasks (e.g., classify objects into one of ten classes), a subtest performance evaluation will test how successfully each of the subtasks is carried out and compare and communicate when performance for some tasks is poor.

Model metric evaluation

Because a wrong or incomplete set of metrics can easily lead to false conclusions about a model's capabilities, the metrics to evaluate a model should always be considered carefully. Classic metrics for classification tasks include, for example, accuracy, precision, recall, or the F1 score (a machine learning evaluation metric that measures a model's accuracy by combining the precision and recall scores of a model). However, many publications include only accuracy without considering other crucial metrics.

Model usability evaluation

Additionally, it is important to keep in mind whether a model can be used on a given hardware setup (computer) for the given task. An object classification model used in autonomous vehicles would use a live classification of the surroundings, performing in real-time. If the model took too much time to evaluate the constant influx of data, it could not perform its task to a satisfactory level (as defined during the planning and development phase).

3.4.3 Dataset transparency

The concept of transparency in the context of machine learning extends beyond AI models. At least as important as the model is the dataset the model learns from. The dataset contains all the information the model “knows” about the world. It defines the so-called knowledge space of the model. The dataset must be chosen carefully based on the task the AI model will be used for. If the dataset lacks data about phenomena about which it should make decisions, it obviously cannot learn to take these decisions reliably.

Misrepresentations in dataset

A dataset should be analysed in terms of relative data distribution. For example, if there are X classes/categories of samples in a dataset (e.g., images of cars, pedestrians and cyclists), does each class occur with the same probability in the pool of data? If there is an imbalance in class distribution, a check should be done to ensure there are enough samples for underrepresented classes so that a machine learning algorithm would still be able to learn from these. This must be checked during sub-task performance testing for the AI model and in case of bad performance should explicitly be noted or the task removed from the promoted capabilities of the model. The learning process could also focus on majority classes and optimise mostly on them, leading to a biased model only suited for processing these majority classes. If these imbalances are detected, appropriate measures must be taken to ensure reliable training of the machine learning approach (e.g., weighted training, under-/over-sampling, etc.). Under-representation of data classes/categories in a dataset must be transparently communicated. If a class needed for a task is heavily underrepresented or even missing, the dataset is unsuitable for the task. Underrepresentation can ultimately only be solved by acquiring more data.

Conditions of data collection

All the conditions relevant to the data generation process for a dataset must be documented and communicated. This ranges from sensor settings, questionnaire design, any secondary influences during data collection (environmental conditions, communication to participants of a study, etc.). Everything directly related to, or happening around, the data collection can potentially provide interesting insights into biases and tendencies introduced into the dataset. Only rich documentation of a dataset allows you to attribute systematic or coincidental influences on the data and possible, otherwise unexplainable, artefacts in it.

Data quality evaluation

Data quality mainly describes the properties of data as **consistent** (regularly sampled, with limited missing data points, few artefacts (e.g., faulty sensor measurement)) and **trustworthy** (with good data documentation, non-tendentious data collection and no meaningful conflicts of interest for the party collecting the data). Data quality must be discussed and openly communicated.

Tendentious data collection and conflicts of interest

There should be full disclosure about potential conflicts of interest of parties involved in dataset creation. This is especially true when it is in their interest to perform tendentious data collection (meaning that they intentionally collect data to show a specific phenomenon). Data collected in this way does not provide a true or representative distribution of the sampled population of subjects/objects from which the data is generated, but instead a biased distribution with a higher probability of showing the searched-for properties. Datasets must be analysed for any biases and for missing or underrepresented phenomena and weaknesses – and be annotated with this information.

3.4.4 Transparency in communication

Transparency also encompasses the communication of generated insights via XAI towards the intended users of these insights (e.g., developers, authorities, end-users). Many insights relevant to optimising the model and its performance can be interpreted for and by developers as they are working directly with the code and model and are skilled experts in the field. They are able to interpret these insights and use them to adapt the model. In the case of different recipients, it is safe to assume that they, as non-experts in the field or in the algorithms used in a specific project, would not be able to interpret what an AI model is designed for.

Information presentation and refinement

Information and explanations sourced from machine learning and XAI models need to be both **perceivable** and **understandable**. These properties follow very different design guidelines when presenting them to different user groups.

Developers and manufacturers gain access to information **at the code level** and can analyse and evaluate insights directly and exhaustively. Explanation techniques should be chosen so that insights into the models are unambiguously and easily provided; it should contain a **non-reduced amount of information**, making everything easy to analyse. Code and insights should be well documented and annotated so that other parties can easily understand the code and work provided. Explainable insights into the model serve developers as they allow them to improve and understand the models used and create a more effective, fair, safe and understandable product. Black-box or obscure models without good XAI methods to gain insights into them would clearly not communicate this necessary information to developers.

For **end users**, the amount and nature of the information provided is very different. Users experience insights from machine learning models while using a technical product (e.g., sitting in an autonomous vehicle) as auxiliary information in contrast to developers, who use these insights directly. End users have limited expertise with AI systems and need insights with **clear, unambiguous images and text/speech**. The information must be presented clearly, be visible or perceivable (digital screen, sounds, etc.) and **compressed in such a way that the user can grasp the meaning** of the insight in the possibly very limited amount of time available in the moment of use (e.g., riding in an AV). This can only be achieved by judging informational relevancy for the end user.

Authorities potentially judging an AI's capabilities to perform given tasks in a public environment **need reports regarding insights that are available both to the developer and to the end user**. This would include full documentation of these insights, originating from the machine learning models used and how they are communicated to developers and end users, as well as models used. The insights should **contain capabilities as well as weaknesses** of the models used, and an honest assessment of what information can be provided and what cannot.

3.5 Using and documenting XAI methods

The variety of models that try to create explanation insights for machine learning models is in the hundreds and is growing due to the great (and increasing) interest in XAI methods which are trying to meet the need for explanations, especially when AI is used in critical applications.

3.5.1 XAI and insight list

It is advisable to obtain a list of the XAI methods that were used to generate insights from a black-box model. Each method should be listed separately, its insights pointed out and the level of explanation (local or global) stated. This list should also be used for any machine learning models that provide levels of explainability themselves (white-box models) as well as their insights. The level of explanation, either global or local, can be incorporated as well. This also helps to identify explanation gaps that could be resolved by introducing additional XAI methods. Table 9 provides an example of an XAI methods and insight list.

Table 9: Sample list of XAI methods used to generate insights from a black-box model, together with insights gained and the level of explanation

<i>XAI methods</i>	<i>Insights</i>	<i>Level</i>
RISE (Petsiuk et al.), 2018 [EXAMPLE]	Highlighting of important pixels in an image given an AI model with classification task; desertion and deletion methods allow validity testing	Local
Method 2	Insight 1 ,2 ,3 ...	Local/Global
...
Method X	Insight 1 ,2 ,3 ...	Local/Global

3.6 Existing work

There are several published approaches which attempt to establish transparency and XAI guidelines for the implementation and use of new AI models (see Table 10).

Table 10: Sample of existing approaches to establish transparency and XAI guidelines.

<i>Tool</i>	<i>Short description and link</i>
Algoritmeregister	Explanation of a public register for AI systems used by the city of Amsterdam which several other European cities also follow. The corresponding white paper contains assessment guidelines for transparency, fairness and ethics of algorithms that should be stored in the register. https://algoritmeregister.amsterdam.nl/wp-content/uploads/White-Paper.pdf
Checklist for explainable AI in the financial sector	White paper providing questions and guidelines in an open-ended format. Contains many general assessments and design ideas for transparent AI solutions; most of them are not restricted to the financial sector https://www.hu.nl/onderzoek/publicaties/a-checklist-for-explainable-ai-in-the-financial-sector
EU AI Act	Law established by the European Union setting many rules and guidelines regarding the future development of AI technologies in the EU. Also contains many guiding principles about what transparent AI solutions should provide regarding explainability, ethics, fairness, robustness and accountability. https://artificialintelligenceact.eu/

4. EVALUATING ACCOUNTABILITY IN AI-BASED CCAM APPLICATIONS

Accountability is a principle under which a person or entity holds the responsibility (“ownership”) for a set of duties in a given context, and s/he can give satisfactory explanations for the actions s/he carries out in that context⁴. According to the OECD.AI Policy Observatory, “Organisations and individuals developing, deploying or operating AI systems should be held accountable for their proper functioning”⁵.

To scope the definition of accountability in AI systems, it is relevant to distinguish user roles in business or project development processes. The Responsibility Assignment Matrix (commonly called the RACI matrix⁶), describes the following main role types:

- **Responsible:** people or stakeholders who do the work. Several responsible people are possible.
- **Accountable:** single person or stakeholder who is the owner of the work (approves when the task, decision or objective is complete).
- **Consulted:** people or stakeholder who need to give permission or input before the work can start and be done.
- **Informed:** people or stakeholders who need to be kept informed about the progress and finalisation of the task.

Although the terms “responsibility” and “accountability” are often used interchangeably, in this context, accountability refers to the ownership of the work while responsibility refers to the assignment of a task.

A related term is **liability**, which refers to being legally accountable for something, with the focus on “paying the cost to repair or mitigate the harm caused by something”, rather than being the owner of the process or product.

In the context of AI-based CCAM, the components for which accountability can be required include **systems and functions**, for which **certification** can provide a level of assurance that required standards are being met and **processes**, for which an **audit** can play a similar role (see Figure 9).

⁴ <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/accountability> and <https://www.britannica.com/topic/accountability>

⁵ OECD.AI Policy Observatory – <https://oecd.ai>

⁶ <https://project-management.com/understanding-responsibility-assignment-matrix-raci-matrix/>

Figure 9: The components of accountability in AI-based CCAM

Accountability can be significantly affected by certification and audit processes, which may provide assurance that a given process, product, or service meets specific requirements. When such requirements are defined by, or drawn from, existing regulations and legal frameworks, the fact of being certified may help determine the ultimate responsibility, accountability and liability of different actors if something goes wrong.

4.1 Accountability checklist

Question	Target Group
Can the data be traced back to the original source?	Developer and Auditor
Are all the transformations of the data being traced, including timestamps? (Added data, removed data, altered data and augmented data)	Developer and Auditor
Are you using any tools for data management?	Developer
Are the actions reproducible?	Developer and Auditor
Does the system ensure that copies of the data cannot be made or if they can, are they being traced?	Developer and Auditor
Are timestamps saved for every action?	Developer and Auditor
Is every action linked to a user/organisation?	Developer and Auditor
Have you looked for existing standards related to the activity being carried out?	Developer
Are you planning to get certified? If so, what certification?	Developer
Is it clearly defined who is responsible, accountable, and liable?	Developer and Auditor

4.2 Current certification processes for AI and CCAM

In this section, three main perspectives are studied regarding certification processes in AI and CCAM. First, **existing norms on AI** are presented. Second, **safety-related norms in the automotive domain** are summarised because of their importance and relevance. Finally, we discuss the **applicability of AI to CCAM** and its impact on certification processes.

4.2.1 Existing norms and certification of AI

Under the new European data strategy, the **EU AI Act**⁷, which was adopted in March 2024, a European law on AI has been proposed that establishes definitions of AI use by categorising applications according to risk levels. These are: unacceptable, high, limited or low/minimal. Products or services using AI with unacceptable risks are prohibited. For the remaining risk categories (especially the high-risk types), the Act defines essential requirements that must be met related to data, governance, technical documentation, logging, transparency and provision of information to users, human oversight, robustness, accuracy and security. These requirements must be ensured during design, development and quality management of the system.

High-risk AI systems are those that can have significant impact on the life of a user, with potential harms caused by its use. These systems are subject to specific obligations and, as such, must pass conformity assessments to be placed on the market. The EU AI Act defines several areas of **high-risk AI systems**. **Self-driving cars** (or AVs) are one of these.

The **regulatory obligations** of the EU AI Act for high-risk systems **fall to the provider that places the product or system on the market**; often the company that develops the AI system is responsible for making sure the system complies. Other stakeholders involved in the distribution, import or use – or other third parties – share “provider” obligations only if they participate in placing the product on the market (under their own name) or change substantially the system itself.

The EU AI Act places obligations on the provider by means of mandatory pre- and post-market actions. The pre-requirements, or conformity assessment, include meeting technical and regulatory requirements, such as putting in place countermeasures against data and model biases, **data governance** principles, provenance, and traceability of data processes through the entire lifecycle of the AI development, testing, deployment and monitoring (see Chapter 5 on privacy). Transparency must be provided, including the capability to enable human oversight over the system (see Chapter 3 on transparency). In general terms, the **requirements defined by the EU AI Act** for high-risk applications are:

- Risk management system for the entire lifecycle
- System tests and definition of mitigation measures
- Data governance principles for data quality
- Technical documentation
- Data logs during system operation (directly related to accountability)
- Interpretability mechanisms towards transparency
- Human oversight, including mechanisms to override and switch off the system.

⁷ <https://artificialintelligenceact.eu/the-act/>

The EU AI Act also defines post-market monitoring obligations for high-risk systems. According to the Act, in case of a violation (e.g., breach in safety laws or fundamental rights), regulators may request access to source code of the AI system, and the product may have to be withdrawn from the market. By contrast, limited-risk applications generally only need to comply with existing product safety and privacy legislation (e.g., GDPR) and preserve the fundamental rights of EU citizens.

Enforcement and implementation of the EU AI Act is driven by the European AI Board, managed directly by the European Commission. Member State regulators are responsible for enforcement and sanctions.

The document **ISO/IEC 5338:2023 AI system life cycle processes**⁸ provides processes that support the definition, control, management, execution, and improvement of the AI system in all its life cycle stages. These processes can also be used within an organisation or a project when developing or acquiring AI systems. When an element of an AI system is traditional software or a traditional system, the software life cycle processes in **ISO/IEC/IEEE 12207**⁹ and the system life cycle processes in **ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288**¹⁰ can be used to implement that element.

Certification of safety functions for CCAM

The automotive industry has generally adopted the **V-Model methodology**, shown in Figure 10, for design and evaluation of automotive functions and systems. Its shape implies direct relationships between development and testing phases, where horizontal axis represents time or project evolution, and the vertical suggests level of abstraction in definition and evaluation.

Figure 10. V-model methodology for design and evaluation of automotive functions and systems

As part of these verification and validation processes, some general requirements and definitions of how to verify and validate them have been established by certification bodies.

⁸ <https://www.iso.org/standard/81118.html>

⁹ [IEEE SA - IEEE/ISO/IEC 12207-2017](#)

¹⁰ [IEEE SA - IEEE/ISO/IEC 15288-2023](#)

ISO26262¹¹ is an international standard for the functional safety of road vehicles. It defines guidelines for the development of safety-critical electronic systems, including automated driving systems. It is a derivative of the more generic meta-standard **IEC 61508** which introduces the fundamentals of functional safety for electrical/electronic/programmable electronic (E/E/PE) safety-related systems, i.e., hazards caused by malfunctioning E/E/PE systems.

The approach taken by this standard is currently being challenged by the emergence of AI systems. The Automotive Safety Integrity Level (ASIL) measurement is a deterministic risk classification that was defined within this standard. It is, however, no longer possible to compute, due to AI's probabilistic nature. This means new norms are needed to meet new needs.

ISO/PAS 21448 SOTIF¹² (safety of the intended function) has been created to address the risks associated with the intended functionality of automated driving systems (as opposed to its malfunctioning). **SOTIF** builds on **ISO26262**, as a complementary standard. It focuses on guaranteeing that automated driving systems are safe and have mechanisms to prevent, control, and/or mitigate safety hazards that can occur without a system failure taking place, in all situations, including those that have not been foreseen. The steps to follow can be summarised as follows:

1. Identify the intended functionality of the system.
2. Identify potential hazardous situations that may occur in reality with the system functioning as intended.
3. Develop scenarios that represent these hazardous situations.
4. Use these scenarios to validate the system.

Case-by-case analysis is required to determine whether a system is suffering a malfunction (hazards caused by a malfunction are assumed to be addressed by **ISO26262**), or if its intended function is satisfied, but a hazardous situation happens nonetheless (which is then covered by the **SOTIF** guidelines). For instance, if a perception system is intended to use camera technologies to detect pedestrians, it is crucial to define the scope of such perception capabilities, usually to be defined by an **Operational Design Domain (ODD)** definition. The ODD describes the conditions and situations under which a system is supposed to function properly. Anything outside of the ODD is also out of scope of the system's intended use.

ISO/IEC TR 5469:2024¹³ enables developers of safety-related systems to appropriately apply AI technologies as part of safety functions by fostering awareness of the properties, functional safety risk factors, available functional safety methods and potential constraints of AI technologies. It also provides information on the challenges and solution concepts related to the functional safety of AI systems.

Certification of AI systems for CCAM

The certification of AI systems for CCAM is still under development as AI technology is very recent, and the CCAM sector is still just emerging. In Europe, the EU has started to address a general regulation framework based on the EU AI Act, which defines a risk-based evaluation approach aiming to ensure that AI systems are safe, reliable, and transparent.

¹¹ <https://www.iso.org/standard/68383.html>

¹² <https://www.iso.org/standard/77490.html>

¹³ <https://www.iso.org/standard/81283.html> <https://www.iso.org/standard/81283.html>

The cycle of processes leading from regulation into standardisation and then certification is complex. The **regulation** (e.g., issued by a public authority) is mandatory, and **provides a legal basis** that describes the goals that must be reached. European **standards** for products and services (driven by private independent organisations) **produce technical specifications** that explain how to reach such goals. **Certification** is then the process by which a third party judges **whether a product or service meets an international or national standard** on a given topic. According to this assessment, a product or service is said to be certified.

While there is no general obligation to implement standards, certification might be required for products in a legally regulated domain, and entities in the industry may decide to use and develop standards together to facilitate meeting the requirement of the certifications. Also, manufacturers and practitioners not implementing standards may need to demonstrate and convince stakeholders that their own technical specifications meet the expected requirements. This process may involve third-party conformity assessment bodies. On the other hand, **products manufactured in compliance with harmonised standards benefit from a presumption of conformity to regulation**, so manufacturers and practitioners may face simplified assessment procedures in comparison¹⁴.

At the time of writing this (2023), there are many standardisation initiatives that address how to comply with this general regulation.

- ITU SG16¹⁵ is working on the use of AI on roads

Published:

- [IEEE 7010-2020](#)TM: Recommended Practice for Assessing the Impact of Autonomous and Intelligent Systems on Human Well-being.
- [IEEE 7000-2021](#)TM: IEEE Standard Model Process for Addressing Ethical Concerns During System Design
- [IEEE P7001-2021](#)TM: IEEE Standards Project for Transparency of Autonomous Systems
- [IEEE P2894](#)TM: IEEE Guide for an Architectural Framework for Explainable Artificial Intelligence

Under development

- [IEEE P2840](#)TM: IEEE Draft Standard for Responsible AI Licensing

Working Groups

- [IEEE P2863](#)TM: IEEE Recommended Practice for Organizational Governance of Artificial Intelligence
- [IEEE P7008](#)TM: IEEE Draft Standards Project for Ethically Driven Nudging for Robotic, Intelligent and Autonomous Systems

The **IEEE CertifAIED**^{TM16} certification programme for assessing ethics of Autonomous Intelligent Systems (AIS) is particularly relevant. While its focus is on ethics, this programme provides a label that helps organisations demonstrate that they are addressing (as ethical values) transparency, accountability, algorithmic bias, and privacy aspects needed to build trust in their systems¹⁷.

¹⁴ [Drafting Harmonized Standards in support of the Artificial Intelligence Act \(AIA\) - CEN-CENELEC 2022](#)

¹⁵ <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/Workshops-and-Seminars/092019/Pages/default.aspx>

¹⁶ <https://engagestandards.ieee.org/ieeecertifaiied.html>

¹⁷ [AI Ethics for Solution Developers.pdf \(ieee.org\)](#)

This programme has been used by the City of Vienna to evaluate an automatic categorisation of incoming customer requests. The general procedure, and its specific application to the Vienna case, is summarised in the following steps:

1. **The company or institution seeking certification** for its product, service or system provides detailed insights to a trusted authority according to the IEEE CertifAIEd guidelines. *Those responsible at the Wiener Stadtwerke (public utility) explained the system to a panel of five IEEE experts, including project background, goals, system architecture, interfaces, machine learning components involved, data used for model training, and expected effects on people.*
2. **The IEEE CertifAIEd programme analyses the system and provides a risk assessment** based on ethical values. *Following the Wiener Stadtwerke information and 26 ethical values (transparency, dignity, trust, avoidance of discrimination, etc.), the panel rated the likelihood of the system to undermine each ethical value considering concrete potential scenarios in the system's deployment. In the Vienna case, the system was rated as low risk for most of the ethical values except for accountability.*
3. **The IEEE CertifAIEd programme defines a risk and conformity assessment procedure** to follow for a specific AI system or service. *43 ethical criteria with brief definitions (e.g., technical aspects such as "error analysis", "hyperparameter tuning", "mitigation of false positives", governance-related aspects such as "adopting a layered approach", "avoidance of inaction", "delay and indifference", etc.) were given to the system owner, who was to provide evidence for each criterion.*
4. **The system under analysis provides evidence on the requested ethical criteria**, structuring the context defined and provided in step 1. This evidence can be in the form of technical documentation, software and hardware implementation details, meeting minutes, deliverables and reports, whitepapers, organigrams, etc.
5. After successful completion, the **company or institution receives a certificate** stating that the product meets the ethical criteria. An assessment report is delivered by IEEE Standardisation Association to the system owner, with specific feedback on each of the ethical criteria from the expert panel members, indicating the degree of fulfilment, areas of improvement, etc.

4.3 Roles and responsibilities

The accountability of AI-based products, services or systems must be addressed against specific roles in the building, deployment, and maintenance process. The main groups of participants, as identified by the IEEE CertifAIEd Ontological Specification¹⁸, are adapted to address the specificities of CCAM applications:

- **Developers:** the entity that designs and develops an AI-based component for a specific purpose. The developer is responsible for the component and all its associated supply chain.
- **Integrators:** the entity that integrates multiple components (potentially from multiple developers) into a complete solution intended for the market (via an operator). Integration includes testing, installing and preparing the solution for its operation.
- **Operators:** the entity that puts the solution into operation.
- **Maintainers:** the entity that monitors and maintains the solution operating under its expected operating values of performance, safety, reliability, sustainability, etc.
- **Regulator:** the entity that enforces standards and laws for the operation and maintenance of the system

Depending on the CCAM application, a single entity may play more than one role, such as integrator and operator. In some cases, it can also be difficult to distinguish between developer and integrator when the supply chain gets complex, and many participants are involved.

4.4 Liability and redress-by-design

In the EU, compensation can be claimed by users of defective products, regulated by a set of product liability rules¹⁹. With the emerging market of autonomous vehicles in Europe, the EU has supported the extension of such regulatory frameworks with legislative acts about liability of automotive products and services, including autonomous vehicles. This includes Directive 2009/103/EC on the insurance against civil liability in respect to the use of motor vehicles, and the **Product Liability Directive**²⁰.

Under this legislation, affected person must prove the defect of the product or service, the damage suffered, and the causal relationship between the defect and the damage. If the cause-effect relationship is demonstrated, the producer of the product or service is liable for the damages under the Product Liability Directive. These laws also establish that EU Member States must ensure that civil liability on the use of vehicles is covered by insurance products. That said, liability can still be claimed against the automaker if it is demonstrated that the defect was caused by a failure to meet safety standards. Linkage between certification processes (to meet safety standards) and liability must still be polished to avoid absurd situations where certain self-driving functions are safety-certified, but not legal in some EU Member States, or vice versa, where lack of legal definition or grey areas may permit autonomous driving functions to be legal but not certified.

¹⁸ [IEEE CertifAIEd™ – Ontological Specification for Ethical Privacy](https://engagestandards.ieee.org/rs/211-FYL-955/images/IEEESTD-2022%20CertifAIEd%20Privacy.pdf) (https://engagestandards.ieee.org/rs/211-FYL-955/images/IEEESTD-2022%20CertifAIEd%20Privacy.pdf)

¹⁹ [Liability for defective products \(europa.eu\)](https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/goods/free-movement-sectors/liability-defective-products_en) (https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/goods/free-movement-sectors/liability-defective-products_en)

²⁰ [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2023/739341/EPRS_BRI\(2023\)739341_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2023/739341/EPRS_BRI(2023)739341_EN.pdf)

Redress-by-design is a means of building accountability directly into a system at the design stage. It relates to the idea of establishing, from the design phase, **mechanisms to effectively detect, audit and rectify any wrong decisions taken by a correctly functioning system**. It can also be used to provide a mechanism for individuals to monitor and challenge harmful conduct by AI systems²¹. This is important for AI systems because the decisions they make are not deterministic, i.e., given the same input, the system may give one output 99% of the time and a different one 1% of the time. Such differences are not a mistake but rather expected behaviour from the system. This means that when we integrate the system, mechanisms should be put in place to deal with these situations.

4.5 Data processing traceability

Data traceability is the ability to **ensure that your data is completely trackable along the entire pipeline**. This allows you to easily follow your data all the way back to its original source. To ensure data traceability, you need to be able to track every transformation in the data that is used and processed. Data lineage tools are commonly used for tracking data from its source to its destination and for providing a detailed history of all the transformations that occur along the way. With a detailed history of how your data has been processed, it is possible to either repeat the whole process for reproducibility (for example for publishing research) or check that every step taken has followed the proper procedure. Reproducibility can also serve as a check for making sure that all actions have been properly tracked.

In the context of data used for CCAM, **developers should use a tool that registers all versions of datasets that are used for the training of the different models used in the vehicles**. It's important to know if and what data was added, removed, filtered, altered, augmented or even copied or downloaded; as well as when and who undertook any of these actions. Registering the user or entity that has made any change to the data is key to ensuring responsibility, accountability and liability. You should also keep track of people either copying or downloading data as they may make changes online that will not be registered by the tracking system. Depending on the data and its content, it may also be wise not to make the data available for downloading and but rather provide a data lake service that makes data available for use but not for local download.

There are several tools that can be used for this purpose, both commercial (DagsHub, Neptune, Weights & Biases, Pachyderm,) and open source (DVC, MLFlow, LakeFS). They generally include data dashboards, reports and exploration tools.

Table 11. Tools for data traceability

<i>Tool</i>	<i>Link</i>	<i>Description</i>
DagsHub	https://dagshub.com/	Commercial tool that offers tracking of data, code, experiments and models.
Neptune	https://neptune.ai/	Commercial tool that offers tracking for data, experiments and models.
Weights & Biases	https://wandb.ai/site	Commercial tool that offers tracking of data, code, experiments and models,

²¹*AI's Redress Problem: Recommendations to Improve Consumer Protection from Artificial Intelligence* by Ifejesu Ogunleye. https://cltc.berkeley.edu/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/AIs_Redress_Problem.pdf

		hyperparameter optimization and automated ML workflows
DVC	https://dvc.org/	Open-source tool for data version control
MLFlow	https://mlflow.org/	Open-source tool for tracking data, models, experiments
Pachyderm	https://www.pachyderm.com/	Commercial tool for data versioning, transformation
LakeFS	https://lakefs.io/	Commercial data versioning

The World Wide Web Consortium (W3C)^{22, 23} issued standards for **data provenance** which can be used for data traceability. They define data provenance as “a record that describes the people, institutions, entities, and activities involved in producing, influencing, or delivering a piece of data or a thing”.

Schreiber et al (2022)²⁴ offer an example from which we can extract some steps to follow for data traceability:

1. **Select the specific objects that need to be tracked**, e.g., whole dataset, individual instance of datasets (images, labels...), users...
2. **Determine what data you want to track** from each object. Typical things to register are timestamps for every action, user ID for the users that access, add or change the data, what data point it affected and the exact action that took place.
3. **Define the required acquisition granularity** for the selected objects. This includes things like:
 - a. Where you get the data from (a server, local machine...)
 - b. At what point in the process (when adding new data, deleting data, modifying it, accessing it, downloading...)
 - c. When you log it (beginning/end/during the process)
4. **Define how you want to structure the information you are saving**. The W3C defines a data model²⁵ centred around provenance that can help with this task.

4.6 Gaps and challenges

As we have seen in the previous sections, and especially in section 4.2 on 4.2 Current certification processes for AI, there is still a lack of standards and regulations in the industry. Regulations are available for functional safety testing but when it comes to AI decision-making systems, **any kind of testing is difficult because the systems are not deterministic**. Normally, a test should indicate how a system behaves in certain situations for the auditing process, but several challenges make this

²² <https://www.w3.org/>

²³ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-dm/>

²⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2022.05.037>

²⁵ <https://www.w3.org/TR/2013/REC-prov-dm-20130430/>

testing difficult, which makes certification or regulation complicated to standardise. Beringhoff et al²⁶ identify 31 major challenges that people from the industry have encountered in testing automated vehicles. Table 12 provides a summary of those challenges and the part of the testing they relate to.

Table 12: Major challenges to testing automated vehicles (source: Beringhoff et al, 2022)

Scenario-based testing	Simulation-based testing	Test automation	Test execution
Terminology (not even the word “scenario” has a standard meaning)	Purely simulation-based sign-off not yet possible (simulation still not the same as reality)	Lack of test automation	Omission of the test driver
Consistent scenario description (OpenSCENARIO is working on this)	Determination of trustworthiness of simulation results	Interaction between test automation, object, and infrastructure	Realisation of test conditions
Complexity of scenarios	Certification of simulation tools	Test implementation effort	Coordination of the surrounding traffic
Multifunctional scenario descriptions (they are needed both for testing and developing, and each task has different requirements)	Identification of simulation-suitable tests		
Coupling scenarios and test cases	Unknown effects (effects that occur but were not added to the simulation)		
Consistent scenario interpretation	Choice of simulation method		
Scenario elicitation. What scenarios are relevant? Difficulty to identify them before release	Lack of simulation models		
Scenario space and use of corner cases	Validation of simulation models		
Scenario generation	Driver models		
SBT on proving grounds (control of traffic, safety concerns, etc.)	Sensor simulation		
Scenario concatenation	Weather effects		
Test end criteria (formalise when enough has been tested)	Integration of the test object in the simulation environment		
Comparison to distance metrics			

While these are not challenges to accountability *per se*, they need to be addressed so that CCAM systems can be properly tested, making it possible to develop certifications for those systems. The certifications, when available, would be as means of assessing accountability.

²⁶ Beringhoff, F., Greenyer, J., Roesener, C., & Tichy, M. (2022). Thirty-one challenges in testing automated vehicles: Interviews with experts from industry and research. In *2022 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV)* (pp. 360-366). IEEE.

5. EVALUATING PRIVACY IN AI-BASED CCAM APPLICATIONS

The European Union’s General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) establishes the level of control that people have over who can access their personal data. The GDPR defines personal data as any information that can be linked to a person. This includes data such as name, identification number, age, location data, etc., that can make a person identifiable. **CCAM developers must keep in mind that it is very likely that the data they collect is personal** and, therefore, subject to GDPR regulations. As such, developers must adhere to the legislation to ensure the responsible handling of personal data in their development of systems in CCAM applications. It is wise to handle your data according to GDPR, even when in doubt about whether it can be considered personal or not.

This protection from the European level means that CCAM developers’ use of personal data is limited. **If information is collected, it can only be used for the specific purposes that the person has given explicit permission to process.** This also implies that the active life of captured data is limited; data should be stored for the minimum possible time. To set the specific period, the organisation should consider why that data is needed, and set a time limit to erase or review it. In addition, only the minimum – and strictly necessary – information should be captured. Stored data should be periodically checked to make sure no unnecessary data is being kept.

Privacy within artificial intelligence (AI) systems should be tackled right from the design phase of development. It must be done so that AI systems always respect the individual’s integrity and **protect their personal data**, assuring responsible collection, processing and use of data. It must also **provide mechanisms to allow the owner of the data to maintain control over their information**, including being aware of what (and how) is being captured and used, and by whom.

This chapter provides a brief description of privacy in CCAM applications, discussions about the gaps found and some guidelines and techniques for building a system that preserves privacy for users.

5.1 Privacy checklist

Question	Target Group
Did you consider the impact of the AI system on the right to privacy?²⁷	Developer/ Auditor
Does the system comply with relevant privacy regulations and standards, such as the GDPR?	Developer/ Auditor
Did you consider the impact of the AI system on the right to physical, mental and/or moral integrity?	Developer/ Auditor
Did you consider the impact of the AI system on the right to data protection?	Developer/ Auditor
Did you establish mechanisms that allow flagging issues related to privacy concerning the AI system?	Developer
Have you considered all type of users whose privacy might be affected? (e.g. drivers, pedestrians, passengers, etc.)	Developer
Is the data personal data?	Developer/ Auditor
Is the data sensitive?	
Is location history stored or shared?	Developer

²⁷ Assessment list for trustworthy artificial intelligence (ALTAI) by the European AI Alliance: <https://rri-tools.eu/-/altai-the-assessment-list-on-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence>

If sensitive data is stored, is it absolutely necessary? And for what purpose?	Developer
Do you have permission or subject consent?	Developer/ Auditor
Is a data map provided, showing what data is collected and how it flows through the system?	Developer
Is the data retention policy described, including how long data is stored?	Developer/ Auditor
Is it explained how user data is used and shared with third parties?	Developer/ Auditor
Can users access, correct, or delete their data? And are these process correctly documented?	Developer/ Auditor
Have you put in place measures to protect user privacy?	Developer
Is user data encrypted, both at rest and in transit?	Developer
Are there access controls to restrict who can view user data?	Developer
What anonymization and/or aggregation techniques does your system use?	Developer

5.2 Regulation of privacy protection

The main regulation in Europe regarding privacy protection is the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)²⁸, which applies to all EU states and extends to organisations outside the EU if they process data belonging to EU citizens. Some key components of the GDPR are:

- **User rights:** Users have the right to request access, correct, or delete the personal information that organisations collect about them. Users can also object to the processing of their data in certain circumstances.
- **Privacy by Design (PbD):** Organisations must proactively incorporate data protection measures into the design and operations of new systems and products.
- **Consent:** Organisations must get explicit consent from users to process their data beyond necessary purposes.
- **Data breach notifications:** If an organisation suffers a data breach, they have 72 hours to notify their supervising authorities of the breach and must inform users as soon as possible.
- **Data Protection Officer (DPO):** Organisations that process a significant amount of personal information need to appoint a DPO, who is responsible for ensuring GDPR compliance.
- **Transparency:** Organisations are required to have a privacy policy that clearly explains how they collect and use personal information.
- **Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA):** DPIAs are required if an organisation's data processing activities could risk the rights and freedoms of individuals.

According to the GDPR, data can only be processed under specific circumstances:

- 1) The subject of the data provides **freely given, specific, informed, and unambiguous consent** to process the data.
- 2) Processing is necessary to execute or to prepare **to enter a contract** to which the data subject is a party.
- 3) You need to process it **to comply with a legal obligation** of yours.
- 4) You need to process the data **to save somebody's life**.
- 5) Processing is necessary **to perform a task in the public interest** or to carry out some official function.

²⁸ [EUR-Lex - 32016R0679 - EN - EUR-Lex \(europa.eu\)](#)

- 6) You have a **legitimate interest** to process someone's personal data. This is the most flexible lawful basis, though the "fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject" always override your interests, especially if it's a child's data.

This highlights that, for CCAM developments, it is **mandatory to always obtain subjects' consent if personal data is being processed by the system.**

Some of the actions that developers and organisations should take according to the GDPR are:

- Appoint a Data Protection Officer (DPO)
- Review privacy notices
- Review consent mechanisms
- Review active contracts with third parties
- Review security measures
- Review the procedures for handling data subject requests

Privacy concerns become significant when dealing with personal data (data that implies the potential to identify an individual or associate data with a specific person). In cases where this association is not possible, regulation of data usage may not be as critical. The GDPR exists to protect individuals from improper use of their data and to ensure their right to privacy. Therefore, the data that is regulated by GDPR is strictly personal data.

Personal data are defined in Article 4 (1) GDPR as: "any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person"

While the aforementioned definition of personal data appears to be accurate, it lacks the specificity that could aid in distinguishing between what constitutes personal data and what does not. The classification of data as personal or non-personal might seem straightforward at first glance. However, the reality is far more complex. This is primarily because it's difficult to envision how such data could be analysed or processed in a manner that ultimately leads to the identification of an individual.

Additional to the classification of data as personal, there are other perspectives to consider. One is "sensitive data". This includes personal data but is considered more sensitive due to the implications when using it. According to the GDPR, Article (9), sensitive data includes personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade-union membership, genetic data, biometric data processed solely to identify a human being, health-related data, and data concerning a person's sex life or sexual orientation.

In the context of autonomous transportation, personal data can be found frequently since you are dealing with people in their roles as drivers, passengers, pedestrians and other actors of the road. Personal data includes images of faces, location, license plates, data related to the driver's use of the vehicle (journeys made, driving style, maintenance, etc)²⁹. Some functionalities of driver monitoring

²⁹ Guidelines 01/2020 on processing personal data in the context of connected vehicles and mobility related applications
https://edpb.europa.eu/system/files/2021-03/edpb_guidelines_202001_connected_vehicles_v2.0_adopted_en.pdf

systems can capture a driver’s health-related data and biometrics. For this reason, it is crucial to exercise caution when collecting data either inside or outside the vehicle. There are several current documents dealing with various aspects of privacy protection in the EU. Those collecting and working with data in the context of AI should be aware of these (see Table 13).

Table 13: Official documents related to privacy protection in the EU

Title	Author	Description	Year	Link
General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	European Parliament and Council of the European Union	A regulation of the European Union (EU) that sets rules for the protection of personal data.	2016	Link³⁰
Ethics of Connected and Automated Vehicles	European Commission	A report by an independent group of experts that includes twenty recommendations on road safety, privacy, fairness, AI explainability, and responsibility for the development and deployment of connected and automated vehicles.	2020	Link³¹
Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI	High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (AI HLEG)	A set of guidelines developed by the AI HLEG to promote trustworthy AI that is lawful, ethical, and robust. The guidelines include seven key requirements for trustworthy AI.	2019	Link³²
Guidelines 01/2020 on processing personal data in the context of connected vehicles and mobility related applications	European Data Protection Board (EDPB)	A set of guidelines developed by the EDPB to provide guidance on the processing of personal data in the context of connected vehicles and mobility-related applications. The guidelines include recommendations on data protection principles, data subjects’ rights, and accountability.	2020	Link³³
ETSI TS 102 941 V1.4.1 (2021-01) Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS); Security; Trust and Privacy Management	European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI)	A technical specification document that outlines the security, trust, and privacy management requirements for Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS). The document provides a framework for the secure exchange of information between ITS stations, including vehicles, roadside units, and central systems. The goal of the specification is to ensure that ITS systems are secure, reliable, and able to protect the privacy of users.	2021	Link³⁴

³⁰ <https://gdpr-info.eu/>

³¹ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/89624e2c-f98c-11ea-b44f-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

³² <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>

³³ https://edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/documents/public-consultations/2020/guidelines-12020-processing-personal-data_en

³⁴ https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_ts/102900_102999/102941/01.04.01_60/ts_102941v010401p.pdf

IEEE P7002™ – Data Privacy Process	IEEE SA Standards Association	The requirements for a systems/software engineering process for privacy-oriented considerations regarding products, services, and systems using employee, customer, or other external users' personal data are defined by this standard. Organisations and projects that are developing and deploying products, systems, processes, and applications that involve personal information are candidate users of the IEEE Std 7002™ standard.	2022	Link
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To ensure privacy, apart from complying with regulations such as the GDPR, data anonymisation or pseudonymisation techniques are required (see Section 5.5). These techniques should be applied either at the point of data capture or when the data is stored on the server.

5.3 Data management and data sharing

CCAM systems must collect and process large amounts of data for correct and safe functioning. This data is not only processed locally but also shared with other road actors or road infrastructure. These systems must handle information such as the vehicle's location, speed, and surroundings, data about the driver and passengers, and road users outside the vehicle as well. Some data can be personal and sensitive, meaning it is important to ensure that it is collected, stored, and shared in a manner that ensures privacy and security in accordance with regulations such as the GDPR to help build trustworthy automated driving systems.

Several types and amounts of data can be involved in a CCAM system. Counting not only an automated vehicle but all the physical and digital infrastructure such as local multi-access edge computing servers, road-side units, traffic lights and other vehicles that are constantly communicating and making data transactions. A great deal of data is captured, processed and sent, and developers must ensure it is correctly managed and protected. The Future of Privacy Forum created a connected cars and data privacy infographic (see Figure 11) providing an overview of the types of data involved in these systems, how it is shared and the different components that can act as data receivers³⁵.

³⁵ Future of Privacy Forum. (2017). *Connected Cars and Data Privacy* [Infographic]. Retrieved from https://fpf.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/06/2017_0627-FPF-Connected-Car-Infographic-Version-1.0.pdf

Figure 11: Overview of the types of data involved in CCAM systems, how it is shared and the different components that can act as data receivers (Source: Connected Cars and Data Privacy)

The European Data Protection Board Guidelines 01/202036 on processing personal data in the context of connected vehicles and mobility-related applications provide a framework for addressing these issues. The guidelines cover topics such as data protection, relevance and data minimisation, security, transmitting personal data to third parties, etc. The general recommendations include:

- **Data processing:** In the context of connected vehicles, most data is considered personal. This includes technical data about the vehicle’s movement and location, as well as data about the vehicle’s condition that can be extracted from its mechanical systems. Data is also collected by camera sensors in the form of images of the driver, passengers, and outside pedestrians. Data can reveal many aspects of the driver and passengers’ lives, including their places of work and residence, the residences of their relatives and friends, their food preferences, and even their religion. To ensure the privacy and security of this data, developers are advised to:
 - **Only collect personal data when it is absolutely necessary.**
 - Adjust the frequency and level of detail of data collection relative to the purpose of processing (some applications may not require frequent data updates).
 - Only activate the collection or processing of data when a specific functionality requests it, rather than collecting it by default.
 - Inform the driver and passengers when and what data is being collected and shared and give them the option to stop the collection of this data.
 - Define a limited storage period or lifetime for data, and/or provide instructions on how to delete it.

³⁶ https://edpb.europa.eu/system/files/2021-03/edpb_guidelines_202001_connected_vehicles_v2.0_adopted_en.pdf

- **Only collect biometric data if it is absolutely necessary for a specific functionality in the context of connected vehicles;** full user control over their biometric data should be guaranteed.
- Provide a non-biometric alternative for accessing functionalities that generally require biometric-based authentication (e.g., starting the engine).
- Ensure that biometric-based functionalities are resistant to attacks.
- Process raw data for biometric purposes in real-time without storing it, even locally.
- Ensure the rights and freedoms of users, by NOT processing or sharing data that could reveal criminal offenses or other infractions (this is forbidden). Manufacturers must not process such data unless a competent authority has authorised it.
- **Purposes for data processing:** Following the GDPR, developers should ensure that their purposes for processing data are **specified, explicit to the user and legitimate**. Asking for consent to collect, process or share the data is mandatory.
- **Data minimisation:** The data collected must be limited to that required for the specific purpose and right functioning of the system. This means **developers should identify the minimum amount of data needed for the proposed purpose of the system**. Doing this ensures the system is compliant with article 5(1)(c) of the GDPR on data minimisation.
- **Data protection:** The services and functionalities developed should be secure as default, as stated in Article 78, GDPR. It includes:
 - Do data processing locally.
 - Do not process personal data and do not transfer personal data outside the vehicle whenever this is possible. There are risks of attacks, leaking of data, etc.
 - Do not allow third party use of data without driver/passenger consent.
 - If external services or applications are integrated, these must ensure the protection of the data.
 - Data should **not be stored more than the purpose of its processing requires it**.
- **Data anonymisation:** Data is considered anonymous when its subject is no longer identifiable. Once it is anonymised, the data is not personal and does not require such strict protection. Anonymising data helps to mitigate the risks of data management. More details about anonymisation techniques are described in Section 5.5.
- **Information:** Developers and service providers should give the driver/passenger information about the person responsible for data collection. This includes giving the contact details of the responsible person, informing about the use of their data, who is collecting it and how it is being processed, the legal basis for the processing, the recipients of the data, where it is processed and stored, if that is the case. Drivers/passengers should be informed of how to request the deletion of their data or how to perform this deletion themselves. This must be done in an easily understandable way, using standardised icons as required under Article 13 and 14 of the GDPR. Developers must also inform users about the consequences of not accepting the sharing of their data, indicating, for example, what functionalities or features would not be available. **A user's objection to data collection should not imply unsafe operation of the vehicle.**

5.4 User authentication / authorisation

Data must be protected throughout its life cycle. All services or systems implemented in the vehicle of CCAM infrastructure should use measures that guarantee the security and confidentiality of data and protect it from unauthorised use. One way to achieve this is to **define a protocol that explicitly indicates the way to access data, who can access what data and in which cases authorisation is permitted**. This protocol should be as detailed as possible while remaining confidential, as it may contain sensitive information about data storage and management that is needed to protect the data itself.

Apart from establishing a protocol and defining user authorisations, the system should be created using a privacy-by-design approach. This means that **privacy is considered and integrated into the design of the system from the very beginning**, rather than being added on as an afterthought. More information can be found in the Guide to Privacy by Design by the AEPD (Spanish Data Protection Agency)³⁷. Some technical measures related to user authorisation are:

- Encrypting data and communication channels
- An encryption-key management system
- User authentication techniques such as passwords, two-factor authentication or electronic certificates to access personal data
- Store a history log of accesses to each data system
- If different roles access the data, different permissions should be given to each of role, with each being as restrictive as possible.

The ETSI TS 102 941 V1.4.1 (2021-01)³⁸ standard defines technical aspects of communication in a CCAM context, including message formats, data structures and authorisation protocols, among others. This is useful to consider when developing services and functionalities that send or receive messages or data (e.g. cooperative awareness systems).

5.5 Federated learning & privacy-preserving techniques

5.5.1 Federated Learning

Standard machine learning approaches require the centralisation of training data on one machine or in a data centre. Federated learning³⁹, by contrast, enables different authorities to collaboratively learn a shared, for instance, prediction model while keeping all the training data on their local devices, decoupling the ability to do machine learning from the need to store the data in the cloud.

Federated learning distributes the machine learning process away from the centre and toward the edge. Training the models locally helps preventing potential data breaches, and the final model is formed in a shared manner by aggregating the local updates. Decentralising the data enables more privacy in the training process as the developers neither need to see the data nor do they need access to it. For sensitive data, or for data coming from countries with different privacy laws, this technique

³⁷ [A Guide to Privacy by Design \(aepd.es\)](https://www.aepd.es/guia-privacidad-dise%C3%B1o)

³⁸ ETSI. (2021). Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS); Security; Trust and Privacy Management. Technical Specification (TS) TS 102 941. European Telecommunications Standard Institute (ETSI). Version 2.1.1

³⁹ <https://ai.googleblog.com/2017/04/federated-learning-collaborative.html>

allows easier development of models that can be used and shared without having to share the data locally with everyone involved.

In the specific case of CCAM, this decentralisation also means if you have a vehicle that captures data, you could train the model in the vehicle and update the general model in the cloud, without having to share the data from the vehicle.

While federated learning is flexible and resolves data governance and ownership issues, it cannot guarantee security and privacy⁴⁰. A lack of encryption enables attackers to steal personally identifiable data directly from the nodes or to interfere with the communication process. Additionally, the decentralised nature of the data complicates data curation to ascertain the integrity and quality of the results. Moreover, if the local algorithms are not encrypted, or the updates are not securely aggregated, data may be leaked, or algorithms tampered with, reconstructed or stolen, which is unacceptable for many applications. Therefore, additional measures are required to protect data from attack strategies such as data poisoning, training data reconstruction (i.e. model inversion) or data interception.

5.5.2 Anonymisation and Pseudonymisation

Another way to deal with data safely is through **anonymisation** or **pseudonymisation**. It's important to differentiate between these two, as pseudonymisation techniques are sometimes erroneously believed to be anonymisation. Under GDPR, the distinction is important: **anonymised data is no longer personal data**, which mean that you don't need to worry about GDPR restrictions. **Pseudonymised data, on the other hand, is still personal** and its use must follow this law.

Pseudonymisation is defined within the GDPR as "*the processing of personal data in such a way that the data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, as long as such additional information is kept separately and subject to technical and organizational measures to ensure non-attribution to an identified or identifiable individual*".

Data can be considered **anonymised** from a data protection perspective when data subjects are no longer identifiable. If the data controller retains the raw data, or any key or other information which can be used to reverse the anonymisation process and to identify a data subject, identification by the data controller must still be considered possible in most cases. Therefore, the data may not be considered anonymised, but merely pseudonymised and thus remains personal data and should only be processed in accordance with the data protection law. Another aspect to consider is that **anonymisation does not last forever**⁴¹. A process that can currently not be reversed may be reversible in the future with technology advancements. Therefore, **the status of data that we now consider anonymised needs to be reviewed periodically**.

Anonymisation is the process of removing personal identifiers, both direct and indirect, that may lead to an individual being identified.

While there may be incentives for some organisations to process data in anonymised form, this technique may devalue the data, so that it is no longer of use for some purposes. Therefore, **before anonymisation, consideration should be given to the purposes for which the data is to be used**.

⁴⁰ <https://blog.ml.cmu.edu/2019/11/12/federated-learning-challenges-methods-and-future-directions/>

⁴¹ [21-04-27_aepd-edps_anonymisation_en_5.pdf\(europa.eu\)](#)

Pseudonymisation is preferable over anonymisation when⁴²:

- The data is being processed for a specific purpose, and some level of personal information is needed to achieve that purpose, but the information should not be directly linked to an individual's identity.
- There is a need to retain some personal information to monitor or enforce compliance with data protection laws, but the data should not be directly linked to an individual's identity.
- The data is being processed for scientific or statistical purposes, and personal information is needed for research purposes, but the data should not be directly linked to an individual's identity.

Table 14 provides some examples of pseudonymisation techniques⁴³.

Table 14: Examples of data pseudonymisation techniques

Pseudonymisation techniques	Description
Encryption with secret key	The holder of the key can easily decrypt the data. All personal data is contained in the dataset.
Hash function	This function returns a fixed size output from an input of any size, and it can't be reversed. The risk is that hash functions are subject to brute force attacks.
Keyed-hash function with stored key	This corresponds to a particular hash function which uses a secret key as an additional input.
Deterministic encryption or keyed-hash function with deletion of the key	This is similar to selecting a random number as a pseudonym for each attribute in the database and then deleting the correspondence table.
Tokenisation	This is typically applied in the financial sector to replace card ID numbers by values that have reduced usefulness for an attacker.

Anonymisation, on the other hand, is preferable when:

- The data is no longer needed for any specific purpose and the data controller has no intention of ever using it again.
- The data is being processed for scientific or statistical purposes, and it is not necessary to retain any personal information.
- The data is being shared with third parties and the data controller has no intention of using the data for any specific purpose.

Table 15 provides some examples of anonymisation techniques.

Table 15: Examples of data anonymisation techniques

Anonymisation techniques		Description
Randomisation	Noise addition	This involves altering attributes to make them less accurate while maintaining the overall distribution. Noise addition is a complementary measure, and it should not be assumed as a standalone solution.

⁴² [What are the Differences Between Anonymisation and Pseudonymisation - Blogpost \(privacycompany.eu\)](https://www.privacycompany.eu/blog/what-are-the-differences-between-anonymisation-and-pseudonymisation)

⁴³ https://ec.europa.eu/justice/article-29/documentation/opinion-recommendation/files/2014/wp216_en.pdf

	Permutation	This technique involves shuffling the values of attributes in a dataset, artificially linking some of them to different data subjects. However, it should be noted that if some attributes have a logical relationship or statistical correlation and are permuted independently, such a relationship will be destroyed.
	Differential privacy	It is an approach for providing privacy while sharing information about a group of individuals. The goal is to describe the patterns within the group while withholding information about specific individuals
Generalisation	Aggregation and K-anonymity	This technique aims to prevent a single data subject from being identifiable inside a group. Their attribute values are generalised so that each individual shares the same value. One way to do this is by using the average value of a certain attribute for all samples.
	L-diversity	This an extension to K-anonymity in which we make sure that every attribute has, at least, L different values.
	T-closeness	This is a refinement of L-diversity where new classes are created that resemble the starting distribution.

5.6 Gaps & Challenges

One key element for adoption of AI technology is the users' trust in the system. This trust is highly influenced by privacy strategies that put users in control of their data and ensure that it is treated properly. While legislation and regulations help guarantee users' rights, there are still some challenges and gaps within a CCAM context.

Current regulations aim to compel car manufacturers to safeguard the privacy of car owners. However, the automotive fleet comprises not only privately-owned cars but also vehicles dedicated to shared use, such as rental cars, transport companies' trucks, taxis, and public transportation. To date, there is no differentiation regarding privacy and consent of use between vehicles that serve different purposes. This lack of distinction brings concerns about the applicability of privacy requirements for different types of vehicles and their uses.

Another challenge arises when passengers in automated cars, who are not the driver and have not given their consent for data capture, have their information collected and processed by the car's active data collection and processing functions. This can occur in carpooling situations, in taxis and in public transportation, where the driver may have accepted the data collection, but the data of others entering the vehicle is processed without their consent. The same issue appears with exterior perception systems that collect data outside a vehicle, capturing information about people in the surrounding area. These individuals, who are unaware and have not explicitly agreed to participate in the data collection, face a privacy breach. These and more concerns are discussed in Yoshizawa et al (2022)⁴⁴.

To ensure a secure CCAM system in terms of privacy, it is essential to consider not only the vehicles but all actors on the road. In these scenarios, smart devices, or other edge servers act as part of the infrastructure, constantly capturing, processing, and transmitting data. These devices face the same challenges as vehicles and must comply with GDPR legislation. As such, they should also be subject to examination to ensure compliance with their obligations to all involved regarding privacy.

⁴⁴ Yoshizawa, T., Singelée, D., Mühlberg, J. T., Delbruel, S., Taherkordi, A., Hughes, D., & Preneel, B. (2022). A Survey of Security and Privacy Issues in V2X Communication Systems. [ACM Computing Surveys, 99\(9\), Article 999¹](#)

One important aspect to consider nowadays is the compatibility of AI and the GDPR, in terms of the GDPR being comprehensive enough to tackle the new algorithms that process data. In general, the report “The impact of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) on artificial intelligence” from the European Parliamentary Research Service⁴⁵ states that the GDPR generally provides meaningful indications for data protection in the context of AI applications. However, since AI-related aspects are not explicitly answered in the GDPR, it may lead to uncertainties and costs, and may discourage the development of AI applications.

AI algorithms require large amounts of data, some of which could be personal, creating a trade-off between having a secure and generalist algorithm and user privacy. This happens not only when collecting data for training; users may want automated functions, assistants or personalised functionalities that require capturing some of their personal data.

These concerns cannot be fully addressed by broad regulations such as the GDPR. Autonomous transportation introduces new scenarios and challenges concerning the privacy rights of individuals. The GDPR, while comprehensive in its attempt to cover various aspects of user data management, can be somewhat vague in its definitions. This vagueness can lead to uncertainties. Indeed, the GDPR states that organisations that process a significant amount of data must appoint a DPO, but it does not define a “significant amount”. Nonetheless, it is likely fair to assume that anyone developing or testing AI-based CCAM functions is dealing with enough data that they should certainly have a Data Protection Officer who can ensure compliance with this regulation.

⁴⁵ European Parliament, Directorate-General for Parliamentary Research Services, Lagioia, F., Sartor, G., The impact of the general data protection regulation on artificial intelligence, Sartor, G.(editor), Publications Office, 2020, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2861/293>

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Annex I

Glossary of terms

When exploring the topic of ethics and fairness in relation to Artificial Intelligence-based Cooperative, Connected, and Automated Mobility (CCAM), several key terms are commonly discussed. The list below provides an overview of the most encountered topics, listed in no particular order, with references to scientific work that has identified them as important in relation to ethics and fairness:

These concepts represent some of the key considerations in the ethical and fair implementation of AI-based CCAM systems. They aim to ensure that the benefits of automation and connectivity are distributed equitably, and that potential risks and biases are minimized. In the present document we will be treating the last four elements identified in detail in separate chapters, and we will only be mentioning their importance and relation to the topic of ethics and fairness in this section.

Term	Definition
Accountability	A set of mechanisms, practices and attributes that sum to a governance structure which involves committing to legal and ethical obligations, policies, procedures and mechanisms, explaining and demonstrating ethical implementation to internal and external stakeholders and remedying any failure to act properly (EPRS 2019).
Agent-deed-Consequence (ADC)	The agent-deed-consequence (ADC) model evaluates moral judgments based on intuitive evaluations of the agent, deed, and consequence, recognizing bad actors but considering mitigating circumstances (Dubljevic, 2020).
Aggregation and K-anonymity	This technique aims to prevent a single data subject from being identifiable inside a group. Their attribute values are generalised so that each individual shares the same value. One way to do this is by using the average value of a certain attribute for all samples.
Aggregation Bias	Occurs when false conclusions are drawn about individual behaviour or characteristics based on observations made at the group level (Jargowsky, 2005) leading to incorrect conclusions about individual behaviours or characteristics. Also known as ecological fallacy.
AI Act	The Artificial Intelligence Act, which adopts a reasonable risk-based approach, establishes uniform guidelines for the creation, introduction to the market, and application of AI systems inside the European Union (AI Act, n.d.).
Algorithmic Bias	There are biases that are introduced by the algorithm itself and are not inherent in the input data. These biases can arise from design choices made in the algorithm, such as the use of specific optimisation functions or regularisation techniques.
Algorithmerregister	Explanation of a public register for AI systems used by the city of Amsterdam which several other European cities also follow. The corresponding white paper contains assessment guidelines for transparency, fairness and ethics of algorithms that should be stored in the register.

<u>Anonymisation and Pseudonymisation</u>	Anonymised data is no longer personal data, which mean that you don't need to worry about GDPR restrictions. Pseudonymised data, on the other hand, is still personal and its use must follow this law.
<u>Automation Paradox</u>	According to the automation paradox, human input becomes increasingly important as an automated system becomes more efficient. Therefore, although human engagement has decreased, it has increased in importance (Karliev, 2023).
<u>Behavioural Bias</u>	Variations in user behaviours across different context or datasets.
<u>Bias</u>	Refers to the unjust favouritism or prejudice towards certain individuals or groups in the design, implementation, or operation of AI systems. Bias can lead to unfair outcomes and discrimination, and it is crucial to address and mitigate it.
<u>CCAM</u>	Cooperative Connected and Automated Mobility is referred to as CCAM. It is therefore a catch-all word for intelligent mobility, often known as smart mobility: cars should be able to talk to each other, be connected to one another and their environment (such as traffic signals), and eventually be able to drive themselves both now and in the future (SWARCO, n.d.).
<u>Conditional Statistical Parity</u>	People in protected and unprotected groups have equal probability of being assigned a positive outcome given a set of related factors.
<u>Content Production Bias</u>	Structural, lexical, semantic, and syntactic differences in the contents generated by users.
<u>Counterfactual Fairness</u>	An individual receives the same outcome with their actual characteristics as when they (counterfactually) belong to another demographic group.
<u>Data Governance</u>	Refers to the responsible and ethical management of data used in CCAM. It includes issues such as data quality, data ownership, consent, data protection, and ensuring that data is used in a manner that respects privacy and avoids unfair discrimination.
<u>Data Protection Impact Assessment</u>	Data Protection Impact Assessments are required if an organisation's data processing activities could risk the rights and freedoms of individuals.
<u>Data Provenance</u>	In the context of computers and law enforcement use, it is an equivalent term to chain of custody. It involves the method of generation, transmission and storage of information that may be used to trace the origin of a piece of information processed by community resources (National Institute of Standards and Technology, n.d.).
<u>Demographic Parity</u>	The chance of being assigned a positive outcome is the same regardless of which group a person belongs to.

<u>Differential Privacy</u>	It is an approach for providing privacy while sharing information about a group of individuals. The goal is to describe the patterns within the group while withholding information about specific individuals.
<u>Distributive Fairness</u>	The equitable distribution of resources among the various members of a community is a matter of distributive justice. According to the notion, everyone ought to possess or have access to about the same amount of tangible things and services (Longley, 2022).
<u>Emergent Bias</u>	Emergent bias occurs as a result of real-world use and interaction with users. This bias arises because of a change in population, in cultural values, or in societal knowledge that emerges after completion of the system design.
<u>End User</u>	An end-user is the person that ultimately uses or is intended to ultimately use the AI system (ALTAI Glossary).
<u>Equity</u>	Refers to fairness and justice in the distribution of benefits and burdens associated with CCAM. It involves ensuring that the benefits of AI-based mobility are accessible to all, regardless of socioeconomic status, race, gender, or other characteristics.
<u>Equal Opportunity</u>	Protected and unprotected groups should have the same rate of being correctly assigned a positive outcome (true positive rate).
<u>Equalised Odds</u>	Both protected and unprotected groups should have equal rates of being correctly assigned a positive outcome (true positive) and being incorrectly assigned a positive outcome (false positive).
<u>Ethical Principles</u>	Ethical principles can be understood as ethical values (e.g., the value of fairness) expressed in normative form (e.g., the principle that public institutions should uphold fairness) (Porter et al. 2023).
<u>Evaluation Bias</u>	Evaluation bias occurs when model evaluation is influenced by inappropriate benchmarks.
<u>Explainability</u>	Explainability is associated with the notion of explanation as an interface between humans and a decision maker that is, at the same time, both an accurate proxy of the decision maker and comprehensible to humans (Barredo et al. 2018).
<u>Fairness through Awareness</u>	Similar individuals (measured by inverse distance metric) receive similar outcomes.
<u>Fairness through Unawareness</u>	No protected attributes are used in the decision-making process.
<u>Federated Learning</u>	enables different authorities to collaboratively learn a shared prediction model while keeping all the training data on their local devices, decoupling the ability to do machine learning from the need to store the data in the cloud.
<u>Hash Function</u>	Hash function returns a fixed size output from an input of any size, and it can't be reversed. The risk is that hash functions are subject to brute force attacks.

<u>Historical Bias</u>	A result of existing biases and socio-technical issues in the world. Can influence the data generation process, even if sampling and feature selection has been done perfectly.
<u>Human Oversight</u>	Refers to the involvement of human decision-makers and supervisors in the design, deployment, and operation of AI systems. Human oversight ensures that ethical considerations and values are taken into account and prevents undue reliance on AI systems.
<u>IEC 61508</u>	Introduces the fundamentals of functional safety for electrical/electronic/programmable electronic safety-related systems, i.e., hazards caused by malfunctioning systems.
<u>IEEE CertifAIEd™</u>	The IEEE CertifAIEd programme analyses the system and provides a risk assessment based on ethical values.
<u>Innovation</u>	Innovation is an activity or process which may lead to previously unknown designs pertaining either to the physical world (e.g., designs of buildings and infrastructure), the conceptual world (e.g., conceptual frameworks, mathematics, logic, theory, software), the institutional world (social and legal institutions, procedures and organization) or combinations of these, which – when implemented – expand the set of relevant feasible options for action, either physical or cognitive (Van den Hofen, 2013).
<u>International Organization for Standardization (ISO)</u>	An international federation of national standards bodies is called ISO (International Organization for Standardization). National standards organizations that work together to produce and promote international standards for a variety of topics, including technology, scientific testing procedures, working conditions, and societal challenges, are members of ISO. Documents describing these standards are then sold by ISO and its members (Loshin, 2021).
<u>International Telecommunication Union (ITU)</u>	ITU is the United Nations specialized agency for information and communication technologies (ICTs). _They enable global connectedness in networks of communication. They design the technical standards that guarantee networks and technologies connect seamlessly, distribute global radio spectrum and satellite orbits, and endeavor to increase access to digital technologies in underprivileged communities across the globe (ITU, n.d.).
<u>ISO/PAS 21448 SOTIF</u>	ISO/PAS 21448 SOTIF (safety of the intended function) has been created to address the risks associated with the intended functionality of automated driving systems (as opposed to its malfunctioning).
<u>ISO26262</u>	ISO 26262 is an international standard for the functional safety of road vehicles. It defines guidelines for the development of safety-critical electronic systems, including automated driving systems.
<u>L-diversity</u>	This an extension to K-anonymity in which we make sure that every attribute has, at least, L different values.

<u>Linking Bias</u>	The uncorrected representation of user behaviour and network attributes obtained from user connections, activities, or interactions. This bias can arise when only considering the links in the network without considering the content and behaviour of users. It can lead to skewed perceptions and biased observations about users.
<u>Longitudinal Data Fallacy</u>	The incorrect analysis of temporal data using cross-sectional analysis instead of longitudinal analysis, which can lead to biased conclusions
<u>Mahalanobis Distance</u>	The Mahalanobis distance, which is employed in discriminant analysis, is a measurement of the distance D between the multiple means (centroids) of the two groups. Both D^2 and T^2 can be used to evaluate the importance of this distance (Riffenburgh, 2012).
<u>Measurement Bias</u>	Arises from how we choose, utilize, and measure features. Measurement bias can occur because of certain intrinsic habits of people capturing data such as poorly trained survey trained interviewers. Another source of measurement bias could be a result of the device used to capture dataset (e.g., Poor quality images captured by camera).
<u>Noise Addition</u>	This involves altering attributes to make them less accurate while maintaining the overall distribution. Noise addition is a complementary measure, and it should not be assumed as a standalone solution.
<u>Omitted Variable Bias</u>	When important variables are left out of the model (Wilms, 2021) because the data is not available, it is difficult to obtain, researchers are not aware of the importance, or intentionally left out due to concerns about the correlation of several independent variables.
<u>Operational Design Domain (ODD)</u>	The ODD describes the conditions and situations under which a system is supposed to function properly. Anything outside of the ODD is also out of scope of the system's intended use.
<u>Permutation</u>	This technique involves shuffling the values of attributes in a dataset, artificially linking some of them to different data subjects. However, it should be noted that if some attributes have a logical relationship or statistical correlation and are permuted independently, such a relationship will be destroyed.
<u>Popularity Bias</u>	Popularity bias emerges when certain items receive more attention or preference, due to their high popularity. It is important to recognise that popularity metrics could be manipulated.
<u>Population Bias</u>	When statistics, demographics, representatives, and user characteristics on the platform differ from the original target population. It leads to non-representative data.
<u>Privacy</u>	Refers to the protection of individuals' personal information and the right to control how their data is collected, used, and shared by AI systems. Privacy concerns arise due to the extensive data collection and processing involved in CCAM.

<u>Privacy by Design (PbD)</u>	A technique called Privacy by Design helps to proactively incorporate privacy into networked infrastructures, business processes, and information technology. The Privacy of Design strategies aim to foresee and stop privacy-invading incidents before they happen.
<u>Procedural Fairness</u>	Procedural fairness is an evidence-based technique that has been consistently linked to higher levels of satisfaction and compliance with judgments made by authoritative figures (National Center for State Courts, 2024).
<u>Product Liability Directive</u>	Part of an extensive EU regulation agenda that also includes the artificial intelligence liability directive, the Product Liability Directive is meant to replace the existing Product Liability Directive 85/374/EEC from 1985. The AI Liability Directive specifically considers advancements in new technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI), new business models for the circular economy, and new international supply chains (Förster & Gashi, 2024).
<u>Redress-by-Design</u>	Redress-by-design is a means of building accountability directly into a system at the design stage. It relates to the idea of establishing, from the design phase, mechanisms to effectively detect, audit and rectify any wrong decisions taken by a correctly functioning system (IPC, 2018).
<u>Robustness</u>	The quality of being strong, and healthy or unlikely to break or <u>fail</u> (Cambridge Dictionary).
<u>Safety</u>	Refers to the prevention of harm to individuals and the environment through the use of AI in CCAM. Safety considerations include robustness, reliability, and fail-safe mechanisms to minimize the risk of accidents or system failures.
<u>Sampling Bias</u>	Arises due to non-random sampling of subgroups and is one of the most common types of dataset bias. Sampling bias can imply trends estimated for one population may not generalize to data collected from a new population.
<u>Self-selection Bias</u>	When research subjects voluntarily choose to participate, leading to a biased sample.
<u>Social Bias</u>	This occurs when others' actions and behaviours influence our judgment.
<u>Socially Robust</u>	"Socially robust" refers to the "due consideration of the context and environment in which the system operates" (EC AI HILEG, 2019).
<u>Subgroup Fairness</u>	Identifies a group fairness metric and applies this test to a collection of subgroups.
<u>T-Closeness</u>	This is a refinement of L-diversity where new classes are created that resemble the starting distribution.

<u>Technically Robust</u>	According to the High-Level Expert Group on AI (2019), the technical robustness of an AI algorithm “requires that AI systems be developed with a preventative approach to risks and in a manner such that they reliably behave as intended while minimising unintentional and unexpected harm and preventing unacceptable harm.
<u>Temporal Bias</u>	Differences in populations and behaviours over time.
<u>Test Fairness</u>	For any value of a predicted probability score, the protected and unprotected groups have equal probability of being correctly assigned to the positive class (true positive rate).
<u>Tokenisation</u>	Tokenisation is typically applied in the financial sector to replace card ID numbers by values that have reduced usefulness for an attacker.
<u>Transparency</u>	Ability for the human user to understand the AI system, including the concepts of interpretability (comprehensible by humans) and completeness (exhaustiveness of the explanation).
<u>Treatment Equality</u>	The ratio of incorrect negative assignments to incorrect positive assignments is the same for both protected and unprotected groups.
<u>Trolley Problem</u>	The term "trolley problem" is often used more loosely to refer to any choice that appears to have a trade-off between what is good and what sacrifices are "acceptable," if at all. It is a fictional thought experiment in ethics about an onlooker having the choice to save 5 people in danger of being hit by a trolley, by diverting the trolley to kill just 1 person (Merriam Webster, n.d.).
<u>Trustworthy AI</u>	Trustworthy AI has three components: (1) it should be lawful, ensuring compliance with all applicable laws and regulations (2) it should be ethical, demonstrating respect for, and ensure adherence to, ethical principles and values and (3) it should be robust, both from a technical and social perspective, since, even with good intentions, AI systems can cause unintentional harm. Trustworthy AI concerns not only the trustworthiness of the AI system itself but also comprises the trustworthiness of all processes and actors that are part of the system’s life cycle (EC AI HLEG, 2019).
<u>Understandability</u>	Understandability (or equivalently, intelligibility) denotes the characteristic of a model to make a human understand its function – how the model works – without any need for explaining its internal structure or the algorithmic means by which the model processes data internally (Barredo et al., 2018).
<u>United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE)</u>	ECOSOC established the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) in 1947. This is one of the UN's five regional commissions. The main objective of UNECE is to advance economic integration across Europe (EU Commission, 2023).

<u>User Interaction Bias</u>	<p>User interaction biases are present in user interactions and, in general, in user behaviour, which can be influenced by both the user interface and the user's own biased behaviour. This bias can manifest in different forms, such as presentation bias, which occurs when the way information is presented influences user choices.</p>
<u>Utilitarianism</u>	<p>Utilitarianism is a tradition in normative ethics that dates back to the English philosophers and economists Jeremy Bentham and John Stuart Mill in the late 18th and early 19th centuries. It holds that an action, or course of action, is morally correct if it tends to bring about happiness or pleasure for all parties involved—not just the one performing the action (Britannica, n.d.).</p>
<u>Value Sensitive Design</u>	<p>A theoretically based method for designing technology that takes human values into account in a thorough and principled way at every stage of the process is called value-sensitive design (Friedmann, et al., 2006). The Value Sensitive Design approach promises to define ethical values throughout the entire (technological) design process with the intention of identifying and resolving ethical conflicts among stakeholders as early as possible.</p>
<u>V-model Methodology</u>	<p>A software development approach known as the V-model explains the connection between every stage of the development life cycle and the testing phase that follows (Oppermann, 2023).</p>
<u>White and Black Box Models</u>	<p>White-box models have interpretable design, which makes their outputs less accurate but easier to grasp. Conversely, black-box models are less interpretable but more accurate (Ali, et al., 2023).</p>
<u>XAI Methods</u>	<p>A collection of procedures and techniques known as explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) enables human users to understand and have faith in the output and outcomes produced by machine learning algorithms (IBM, 2023).</p>

Annex II

Overview of moral principles

Table 16 provides an overview of these moral core principles with a brief explanation of their meanings and extends the core set with other relevant principles identified as key elements for ensuring that the development and deployment of AI-based CCAM technologies are human-centred. The final three principles are not, for the moment, labelled as human rights, but we agree with the authors on their importance in ensuring the wellbeing of humans when interacting with CCAM technologies.

Table 16. Moral principles needed for the development and deployment of human-centred AI-based CCAM technologies

<i>Principle</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Source(s)</i>
Respect for human dignity	<p>Every individual human possesses intrinsic worth that should not be violated or traded for the achievement of any other ends (EC, 2020).</p> <p>AI systems should respect, serve and protect humans' physical and mental integrity, personal and cultural sense of identity, and satisfaction of their essential needs (1; 2).</p> <p>In relation to CAVs, respecting human dignity requires that fundamental individual rights are not infringed upon or sacrificed in the name of other societal good. (EC, 2020)</p>	AI HLEG, 2018 EC, 2020 AI 4 People IEEE
Freedom of the Individual	<p>Mitigation of (in)direct illegitimate coercion, threats to mental autonomy and mental health, unjustified surveillance, deception and unfair manipulation. (AI HLEG, 2018)</p> <p>Autonomous and Intelligent Systems (A/IS) should be designed and operated in a way that both respects and fulfils human rights, freedoms, human dignity, and cultural diversity (IEEE).</p>	AI HLEG, 2018 AI 4 People IEEE
Respect for democracy, justice and the rule of law	<p>"AI systems should serve to maintain and foster democratic processes and respect the plurality of values and life choices of individuals" [...] and "ensure that they do not operate in ways that undermine the foundational commitments upon which the rule of law is founded, mandatory laws and regulation, and to ensure due process and equality before the law". (AI HLEG, 2018)</p>	AI HLEG, 2018 IEEE
Equality, non-discrimination and solidarity	<p>"System's operations cannot generate unfairly biased outputs (e.g., the data used to train AI systems should be as inclusive as possible, representing different population groups). This also requires adequate respect for potentially vulnerable persons and groups, such as workers, women, persons with disabilities, ethnic minorities, children, consumers or others at risk of exclusion." (AI HLEG, 2018), similarly expressed in (EC, 2020).</p> <p>"CAVs should provide equality of access to mobility for all and should be calibrated by developers to reduce disparities in exposure to harm between categories of road users." (EC, 2020)</p>	AI HLEG, 2018 EC, 2020 AI 4 People IEEE XAI & AVs (India)
Right to explanation	<p>Transparency and communication of the underlying functionality, which can be achieved through accountability measures such as audits and logging mechanisms. (AI 4 People)</p>	AI 4 People XAI & Avs (India)
Right to protection of personal data	<p>Data ownership, data governance and privacy of personal data that is generated during the operation of self-driving cars. (AI 4 People)</p>	AI 4 People Explainable AI

		XAI & Avs (India)
Technology misuse and awareness of it	New technologies entail the risk of misuse, and the principles of responsible innovation require public education and awareness of these risks (IEEE).	IEEE
Prioritise wellbeing	The principle of wellbeing applies to humans and the environment, individuals and societies, present and future conditions (AI HLEG 2019). Well-being is an essential indicator for quality of life and societal progress (IEEE).	AI HLEG, 2018 EC, 2020 IEEE
Accountability	Includes the duty to explain the behaviour of AVs (EC, 2020). Accountability is enhanced with transparency (IEEE).	EC, 2020 IEEE

Summary of principles and requirements for ethical AI

Continuing the discussion on the synthesis of the guidelines for ethical principles in AI (i.e., Table 4 in Chapter 1), the table below summarizes the principles and requirements for ethical AI based on different parameters.

Table 17: Summary of sources of principles and requirements for ethical AI

Principles/Requirements									
	CPAIS 2019	IEEE 2019	Turing 2019	EC AI HILEG, 2019	EC Ethics of CAVs, 2020	UNESCO, 2021	AI4People, 2021	OECD, 2022	No. of mentions
Number of principles	1	8	5	11 (4 principles, 7 requirements)	8	10	7	5	
Diversity/Fairness/Justice/ Non-Discrimination			Yes (incl. discriminatory non-harm and data, design, outcome, implementation fairness)	Yes (incl. substantive and procedural dimension as a principle, avoidance of unfair bias, accessibility and universal design, stakeholder participation as a requirement)	Yes (incl. fair distribution of benefits and burdens)	Yes (incl. non-discrimination, inclusive access, solidarity)	Yes (incl. avoidance of unfair bias, responsible balancing of risks and accessibility)	Yes (incl. human-centred values)	6
Sustainability/Well-Being		Yes (incl. quality of life)	Yes	Yes (requirement, incl. sustainability and environmental friendliness, social impact, society and democracy)		Yes	Yes (incl. societal and environmental well-being, sustainability, environmental friendliness, social impact)	Yes (incl. inclusive growth and sustainable development)	6
Transparency		Yes (incl. traceability, explainability, interpretability)	Yes (incl. process and outcome transparency)	Yes (incl. explicability as a principle, incl. traceability, explainability, communication as a requirement)		Yes (incl. explainability)	Yes (incl. communication, affirmative and explicit consent, limited third-party sharing, compliance with regulations)	Yes (incl. explainability, responsible disclosure)	6
Accountability		Yes (incl. responsibility and culpability)	Yes (incl. answerability and auditability)	Yes (requirement, incl. auditability, minimisation and reporting of negative impact, trade-offs, redress)			Yes (incl. automation, transparency measures, reporting of negative impact, redress)	Yes	5
Technical Robustness/Safety			Yes (incl. accuracy, reliability, security, robustness)	Yes (requirement, incl. resilience to attack and security, fall back plan and general safety, accuracy, reliability and reproducibility)		Yes (incl. human, environmental, ecosystem safety and security)	Yes (incl. resilience to attack, security, fallback plan, general safety, accuracy, reliability)	Yes (incl. traceability, systematic risk management)	5
Autonomy/Human Agency/Oversight				Yes (incl. self-determination and human oversight as a principle, incl. fundamental rights as a requirement)	Yes (incl. personal autonomy, human moral agency)	Yes (incl. individual and public oversight, human determination)	Yes (incl. monitoring, training, human-machine interfaces, external control of vehicle data)		4
Data Agency/Data Governance/Privacy		Yes (incl. privacy and consent)		Yes (principle, incl. respect for privacy, quality and integrity of data, access to data)		Yes (incl. data protection)	Yes (incl. respect for privacy, transparency, communication, access to data)		4

Non-Maleficence/Prevention of Harm				Yes (principle, incl. protection of human dignity, mental and physical integrity, technical robustness)	Yes (incl. integrity of human beings, other living beings and the planet)	Yes (incl. proportionality and appropriateness, foundational values and human rights, scientific foundations)			3
Human Rights/Dignity		Yes			Yes (incl. fundamental individual rights)				2
Responsibility					Yes (incl. moral and legal responsibility)	Yes (incl. accountability)			2
Inclusive Deliberation/Multi-Stakeholder Governance/Collaboration					Yes	Yes (incl. respect for international law and national sovereignty, inclusion, adaptation)			2
Awareness		Yes (incl. awareness of misuse and risks)				Yes (incl. literacy)			2
Trust/Distrust	Yes								1
Effectiveness		Yes (incl. fitness for purpose)							1
Competence		Yes							1
Solidarity					Yes (incl. pro-social actions and practices, institutional and political regulations)				1
Beneficence					Yes (incl. positive welfare contribution)				1
Reference to implementation of principles	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Includes policy recommendations	No	Yes	Yes	No (published in separate document)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Usable as a checklist	No	No	Yes (for implementation of human-centred AI projects)	Yes (as pilot version for assessment of trustworthy AI, expanded in EC AI HLEG ALTAI 2020)	No	No	Yes (esp. for policymakers and companies as well as for developing an ethics certification)	No	